

VALKYRIES

D4.3 Roadmap for enhancing the pan-European technological capabilities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters

Reference Number: D4.3

Ed/Rev: A/0

Main Contributor: UMU

**Other Contributors: INDRA, SERMAS, TASSICA, ISEMI, SSSA,
BC2050, BDI, KEMEA, HESE, ARATOS, USN, AREU, NOVOTEC,
PARTICLE**

Date: 31/03/2022

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101020676

Editors

Name	Contact	Entity
Sergio López Bernal	slopez@um.es	UMU
Manuel Gil Pérez	mgilperez@um.es	UMU
Gregorio Martínez Pérez	gregorio@um.es	UMU
Eduardo López Bernal	eduardo.lopez5@um.es	UMU
Juan Antonio Martínez López	juanantonio.martinezl@um.es	UMU
Pedro Beltrán López	pedro.beltranl@um.es	UMU

Contributors

Name	Entity	Contribution
Ignacio Hernández	NOVOTEC	Methodology, Review
Pedro Miguel	PARTICLE	Chapter 8, 9, 10, 11; OP4.4, OP4.14, OP4.15, OP4.16
Marco Manso	PARTICLE	Chapter 8, 9, 10, 11; OP4.4, OP4.14, OP4.15, OP4.16
José Pires	PARTICLE	Chapter 8, 9, 10, 11; OP4.4, OP4.14, OP4.15, OP4.16
Beata Korpesio	ISEMI	Chapter 7.1 (CO.WP4.38, CO.WP4.41), Chapter 9.2
Alberto Montarelo	TASSICA	Contribution in common DX.3 deliverable introduction and methodology. CO.WP4.28, CO.WP4.42, CO.WP4.21
Luis Fernando Moro	INDRA	CO.WP4.13, CO.WP4.23, CO.WP4.33, CO.WP4.42, CO.WP4.18
Ioannis Chatzichristos	ARATOS	CO.WP4.46, CO.WP4.47 as in CO.WP4.55 clustered
Antonio Calero	INDRA	CO.WP4.17, CO.WP4.24, C.O.WP4.42. Chapter 9.2, Chapter 11.2
Per Haavardtun	USN	CO.WP4.2 contributions to 8.1 and 8.2
Denise Amram	SSSA	CO.WP4.39 and CO.WP4.40
Miguel Gaspar	HESE	CO.WP4.32 and CO.WP4.53
José Cabezas	NOVOTEC	CO.WP4.35, CO.WP4.36 and CO.WP4.37
Maya Bozhilova	BDI	CO.WP4.10 and CO.WP4.44; Contributions to Sections 8.1 and 8.2
John Tsaloukidis	KEMEA	CO.WP4.25; Contribution to Section 7.1
Eduardo López Bernal	UMU	CO.WP4.21; Contribution in chapter 5,6,7,8,9,10 and 12
Juan Antonio Martínez López	UMU	CO.WP4.21; Contribution in chapter 5,6,7,8,9,10, and 12
Pedro Beltrán López	UMU	CO.WP4.21; Contribution in chapter 5,6,7,8,9,10, and 12
Andrea Comelli	AREU	CO.WP4.29 - CO.WP 4.52 - CO.WP 4.54
Sergio López Bernal	UMU	CO.WP4.21; Contribution in chapter 5,6,7,8,9,10, and 12
José Cabezas Rodríguez	NOVOTEC	Methodology, Review
Manuel Ocaña	INDRA	Quality Review

Document Changes Record

Edit./Rev.	Date	Chapters	Reason for change
A/0	31/03/2023	All	Original Document

Content

1.	Executive Summary	1
2.	Identification	2
3.	Introduction	3
3.1.	Objective	3
3.1.1.	Structure criteria Methodology (common)	3
3.1.2.	ID Codification/Traceability (common)	3
3.2.	Exclusion criteria	4
3.3.	Experts consultation.....	4
4.	Taxonomy process (common)	5
5.	Clustering opportunities.....	6
6.	Opportunities analysis.....	11
6.1.	Methodology (common)	11
6.2.	Opportunities rating according to the questionnaire	12
6.3.	Opportunities matrix.....	34
7.	Opportunity ranking in WP4	36
8.	Identify interdependences	40
8.1.	Inside of the WP4	40
8.2.	Between the WPs.....	42
9.	Evaluation in short of top ranked opportunities.....	46
10.	Roadmap for pre-standardisation.....	48
10.1.	WP roadmap.....	48
10.2.	Opportunity roadmap	49
10.2.1.	CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles	49
10.2.2.	CO.WP4.28: Cross border data trace	50
10.2.3.	CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges.....	51
10.2.4.	CO.WP4.55: Use of wearable to support triage.....	53
10.2.5.	CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms	54
10.2.6.	CO.WP4.2: Logistics assistances using UAVs.....	56
11.	Stakeholders' evaluation.....	58
12.	Conclusions	61
12.1.	Conclusions CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles	61
12.2.	Conclusions CO.WP4.28: Cross border data trace	61

12.3.	Conclusions CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges.....	61
12.4.	Conclusions CO.WP4.55: Use of wearable to support triage.....	62
12.5.	Conclusions CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms	62
12.6.	Conclusions CO.WP4.2: Logistics assistances using UAVs.....	63
13.	Annex A – References and bibliography	64
14.	Annex B – Glossary	65

Tables

Table 1 - ID gaps and opportunities codification structure for traceability.	4
Table 2 - ID clustered opportunities codification structure for traceability.	4
Table 3 - WP4 opportunities after the clustering.	10
Table 4 - Questions related to the feasibility of the opportunities.	11
Table 5 - Questions related to the impact of the opportunities.	11
Table 6 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.1: Up to date information about the environment, detecting imminent risks for patients and first responders.	13
Table 7 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.2: Logistics assistance using UAVs. ...	13
Table 8 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.3: Conduct search and relief missions.	13
Table 9- Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.4: Use of communication systems able to provide alternative communication capabilities, being also compatible with existing communication technologies using gateways.....	14
Table 10 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.5: Use of technologies that allow the adaptability of the network architecture, ensuring data availability.	14
Table 11 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.6: Selection of technologies based on the type of data to be transmitted.....	15
Table 12 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.7: Use of technologies and guidelines that favour the extension of communication coverage in emergency situations.....	15
Table 13 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.8: Creation of communication preference mechanisms in the networks available during the emergency.	16
Table 14 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.9: Use of regulations and communications technologies that ensure data privacy and security during data sharing. There is also an opportunity for implementing better control access mechanisms during data sharing.	16
Table 15 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.10: Use of guidelines and protocols to provide data backup.....	17
Table 16 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.11: Structured management of information coming from different sources.....	17
Table 17 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.12: Definition of standards regarding user devices specifications and their usage.	17
Table 18 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.13: VR debriefing systems.	18
Table 19 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.14: Multiplatform. Run different OS.	18
Table 20 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles	18
Table 21 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.16: Georeferenced recording of events on the ground.....	18

Doc title: Roadmap for enhancing the pan-European technological capabilities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters

Table 22 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.17: HUMS (Health and Usage Monitoring Systems) or simulators for boosting forces. 19

Table 23 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.18: COP standardisation. 19

Table 24 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.19: Asset’s responsiveness and being able to adapt to fast-changing environments, mission needs and scenarios. 20

Table 25 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.20: Detecting trends and achieving maximum operative readiness. 20

Table 26 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms. 21

Table 27 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.22: Social Network data visualization C2. 21

Table 28 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.23: Open Source C2 App. 22

Table 29 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.24: Satellite weather data recorded in Hybrid Digital Twins as a layer. 22

Table 30 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.25: Common Operational Picture exchange. 22

Table 31 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.26: Guidelines for social media crawling. 23

Table 32 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.27: Airspace coordination with drones. 23

Table 33 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.28: Cross border data trace. 24

Table 34 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.29: Victims advance information. ... 24

Table 35 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.30: Victims’ historical data. 24

Table 36 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.31: External data. 25

Table 37 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.32: Guidelines for identifying dangerous zones. 25

Table 38 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.33: Identification of relevant locations. 25

Table 39 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.34: Use of decision-making applications using AI-based systems. 26

Table 40 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.35: Creation of operating procedures. 26

Table 41 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.36: Incorporation of new standards. 27

Table 42 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.37: EDXL HAVE Standard. 27

Table 43 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.38: Digital Skills Improvement. 27

Table 44 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.39: European Iconographic Standardisation. 27

Table 45 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.40: European data standardisation. 28

Table 46 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.41: Device’s upgrade. 28

Table 47 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges. 29

Table 48 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.43: Placing FR as an important focus on the design of solutions. 29

Table 49 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.44: Instant access with transparency to Crucial information in a secure way. 29

Table 50 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.45: Best practice for introducing the e-tools where it is missing. 30

Table 51 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.46: Use of wearables to obtain information about patients and first responders, about the environment, and manage alerts. 30

Table 52 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.47: Creation of wearable prototypes using own technologies.	31
Table 53 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.48: Strategies for battery saving in wearables.	31
Table 54 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.49: Novel communication system between first responders using wearables.	32
Table 55 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.50: Patient vital signs management and interoperability for healthcare.	32
Table 56 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.51: Define a telemedicine service during emergency actuations.	32
Table 57 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.52: European Health Data Space....	33
Table 58 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.53: Use of wearables on critically ill patients.	33
Table 59 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.54: Manufacturing wearables according to medical regulations.	34
Table 60 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.55: Use of wearables to support triage.	34
Table 61 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.56: Technology update business services model.	34
Table 62 - Ranking of all WP4 opportunities after the clustering.	39
Table 63 – Evaluation of the opportunity CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles.	46
Table 64 - Evaluation of the opportunity CO.WP4.28: Cross border data trace.	46
Table 65 - Evaluation of the opportunity CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information.	46
Table 66 - Evaluation of the opportunity CO.WP4.55: Use of wearables to support triage.	47
Table 67 - Evaluation of the opportunity CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms.	47
Table 68 - Evaluation of the opportunity CO.WP4.2: Logistics assistance using UAVs.	47
Table 69 - Answers given by EABs consultation in the questionnaire.	60
Table 70 - Glossary	65

Figures

Figure 1 - Example of a feasibility-impact matrix.	12
Figure 2 – WP4 clustered opportunities feasibility-impact matrix.	35
Figure 3 - WP4 clustered opportunities selecting the 6 top-ranked.	35
Figure 4 - WP4 interdependencies, where each opportunity indicates the list of opportunities on which it depends.	42
Figure 5 - Interdependences between WP4, WP5, and WP6.	45
Figure 6 - General roadmap steps.	48
Figure 7 - Roadmap for CO.WP4.15 Location of near/nearest Vehicle.	49
Figure 8 - Roadmap for CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges.	51
Figure 9 - Roadmap for CO.WP4.21 Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms.	54
Figure 10 - Roadmap for CO.WP4.21 Logistics assistance using UAVs.	56

This page intentionally left blank

1. Executive Summary

Deliverable D4.3 - Roadmap for Enhancing Pan-European Technological Capabilities for First Aid Response on Multi-Casualty Disasters begins by presenting a clustering of opportunities obtained in D4.6 (1), where opportunities with similar features have been grouped together.

Next, the document analyses all opportunities generated by the clustering. The analysis involves evaluating each opportunity based on their scores in impact and feasibility obtained from questionnaires completed by all partners in the VALKYRIES Consortium. Furthermore, the opportunities are ranked based on their scores to determine the most suitable ones to implement in the use cases that will be performed in this project. For WP4, six opportunities have been selected.

Subsequently, the report presents a list of interdependencies for each selected opportunity among the top-ranked opportunities in WP4, WP5, and WP6. Additionally, the document briefly explains how and why the chosen opportunities should be implemented.

Finally, the deliverable presents proposed roadmaps for pre-standardising each selected opportunity. The roadmaps indicate the necessary steps and their corresponding deadlines that need to be completed.

(Common points through deliverables)

Due to the horizontality of the project at this stage and the similarities in work packages 4, 5 and 6 a common work methodology has been established for them. This allows to intercompare results between work packages, to be efficient and to provide a holistic result.

For these reasons a common TOC has been established for deliverables 4.3, 5.3 and 6.3. Some chapters are common to these deliverables, which is why they are marked in their title as (common).

2. Identification

Deliverable Title: Roadmap for enhancing the pan-European technological capabilities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters.

Deliverable Id: D4.3

Deliverable Title Abbreviation: D4.3

Name of lead participant: UMU

Name of Contributors: INDRA, SERMAS, TASSICA, ISEMI, SSSA, BC2050, BDI, KEMEA, HESE, ARATOS, USN, AREU, NOVOTEC, PARTICLE

Type: Report (R)

Dissemination Level: Public (PU)

Proposed Classification Level: Non-Restricted

Reporting Conditions: Funding Requirement (FR)

Linked project Work Package: WP4

Linked project tasks: T4.1, T4.2, T4.3, T4.4, T4.5

Action: Study

Status: First Release

Document Layout: Custom layout

Details: This specification applies to the project VALKYRIES: Harmonization and Pre-Standardisation of Equipment, Training and Tactical Coordinated procedures for First Aid Vehicles deployment on European multi-victim Disasters funded under the SU-DRS03-2018-2019-2020 (IA), subtopic 3 Grant Agreement of the Horizon 2020 (H2020) tendering conditions. The document presents an analysis, prioritisation and scheduling of the evolution and adoption of new technological capabilities for first aid responses in the EU.

3. Introduction

This section presents the methodology followed during the elaboration of this deliverable, which is helpful to understand and recreate the findings of this document. It also explains the structure of the document, which has been agreed upon and shared between the deliverables of WP4, WP5 and WP6. After that, it presents the exclusion criteria followed, highlighting essential aspects to understand which data have yet to be considered and why. Finally, a brief explanation of the validation was given by experts.

3.1. Objective

The main objective of the H2020 VALKYRIES project is the development, implementation, validation and application of innovative theoretical foundations, methods, prototypes and their demonstration on a reference integration for supporting the ongoing/planned European actions for pre-standardisation and harmonisation technologies, procedures, preparedness and cross-sector/border cooperation and education and training for first aid response at disaster management by emergency health services, with the focus on their vehicular deployments.

3.1.1. Structure criteria Methodology (common)

The methodology for developing deliverable D4.3 was commonly agreed upon among the leaders of WP4, WP5 and WP6, and it is common for deliverables D5.3 (2) and D6.3 (3). NOVOTEC as framework harmonisation and INDRA as project leader supported this process.

The methodology and the structure of this document include the following sequential steps:

- Taxonomy process
- Clustering of the of identified harmonization opportunities in the deliverables D4.2 (first version) (4) and D4.6 (final version).
- Harmonized analysis of the opportunities, which is based on the feasibility-impact matrix.
- Analysis of the results of the matrix and explanation.
- Opportunities matrix with the results.
- Opportunities ranking.
- Interdependences with other opportunities.
- Evaluation in short analysis.
- Roadmap for work package and for opportunity.
- Stakeholders' evaluation.
- Conclusions.

3.1.2. ID Codification/Traceability (common)

To ensure traceability of gaps, opportunities and grouping of opportunities between WPs. A codification of each of the topics to be addressed has been carried out.

Gaps and opportunities codification

In this deliverable D4.3, the coding of gaps and opportunities established in D4.2 (draft version) and D4.6 (final version) is maintained for ease of reading and to establish a link between the different work packages and deliverables of the Project.

1 st part	2 nd part	3 rd part	4 th part
G=Gap OP= Opportunity	Task number	-	Item number (1..n)
Example			
G	4.1	-	1

Table 1 - ID gaps and opportunities codification structure for traceability.

Clustered Opportunities codification

It has been established a coding for clustered opportunities formed based on the original opportunities. Following the above structure, they are formed according to the following table:

1 st part	2 nd part	3 rd part	4 th part
CO= Clustered Opportunities	Work package number	-	cluster number (1...n)
Example			
CO	WP4	-	1

Table 2 - ID clustered opportunities codification structure for traceability.

3.2. Exclusion criteria

All the gaps and opportunities included in D4.2 (draft version) and D4.6 (final version) have been considered for the initial works on this deliverable. Once the ranking of the clustered opportunities is established, according to the methodology described for the present deliverable, the work of the deliverable focuses on the top opportunities selected.

3.3. Experts consultation

The results of the harmonization and pre-standardisation tasks have been subjected to internal validation processes with the most expert project researchers in each case, consultation with the External Advisory Board (EAB) and, in some cases, external validation with experts from outside the project.

4. Taxonomy process (common)

Deliverable D2.2 "Terminology and semantics" (5) provides a unified glossary, and a map of joint terminologies and semantic representations focused on the specificities of cross-sectoral, cross-border and cross-hierarchical action against European multi-victim disasters. The objective is to support the harmonization, pre-standardisation, and standardisation efforts of first responders in disasters. Deliverable D2.2 has been based on the proposal, debate, discussion, and consensus of the different terms and has been kept alive during the whole life cycle of the Project, serving as a constant reference for the researchers in their work and the drafting of the respective deliverables.

Following this consensus, for work D4.3, the researchers reviewed the terminology used in relation to the statements and contents of the opportunities detected to homogenize them. This facilitated the grouping of similar opportunities and the study of interdependencies between related opportunities inside and outside the WP, a fundamental aspect in the analysis, prioritization and roadmap for the evolution and adoption of new standard practices and procedures for first responder responses in the EU environment.

This process has been carried out the same way in developing the works leading to deliverables D5.3 and D6.3 of the Project.

5. Clustering opportunities

In deliverable D4.6 - Harmonization opportunities on the technological landscape for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters, a total of 132 opportunities were found related to WP4. Valkyries partners analysed in depth all opportunities to evaluate similarities and differences between them to group the opportunities focused on the same category.

Consequently, those presenting common aspects were grouped, generating a new meta-opportunity (also called clustered opportunity). Thus, a total of 56 meta-opportunities were defined where each one can be composed of one or more opportunities that are related to each other. Table 3 shows on the left column the new meta-opportunity and on the right column, the opportunities that composed it.

Opportunities	Merged opportunities
CO.WP4.1: Up to date information about the environment, detecting imminent risks for patients and first responders.	OP4.1-1: Accurate and live weather data OP4.1-2: Up to date information about terrain and infrastructure in the disaster areas. OP4.1-4: Safe work environment for first responders. OP4.5-14: Integration of sensors for hazardous substances. OP4.3-16: Drones' imagery data OP4.3-17: Obtain high ground resolution data.
CO.WP4.2: Logistics assistance using UAVs.	OP4.1-6: Distribution of equipment. OP4.1-7: Supply energy and charging capabilities.
CO.WP4.3: Conduct search and relief missions	OP4.1-8: Conduct search and relief missions
CO.WP4.4: Use of communication systems able to provide alternative communication capabilities, being also compatible with existing communication technologies using gateways.	OP4.1-5: Build ad hoc communication grids. OP4.2-1: Use of alternative communication systems. OP4.2-7: Use of balloons to create communication routes in rural or poor coverage areas. OP4.2-12: Use of technologies based on security constraints. OP4.2-17: Developing national ad hoc emergency networks. OP4.2-21: Bridge between networks. OP4.2-23: GATEWAY. OP4.2-24: IP LAYER. OP4.2-26: Data Conversion. OP4.5-35: D2D network gateway. OP4.3-19 RF space management.
CO.WP4.5: Use of technologies that allow the adaptability of the network architecture, ensuring data availability.	OP4.2-3: Use of technologies that allow the adaptability of the network architecture. OP4.2-18: Leveraging 5G networks. OP4.2-25: Data Priority OP4.2-27: Communications redundancy OP4.2-28: GATEWAYS networks OP4.2-29: Data cluster OP4.2-31: APPS/Functions redundancy OP4.2-32: Block Chain redundancy. OP4.5-19: Record victim's data in blockchain

Opportunities	Merged opportunities
CO.WP4.6: Selection of technologies based on the type of data to be transmitted.	OP4.2-8 Selection of technologies based on the type of data to be transmitted.
CO.WP4.7: Use of technologies and guidelines that favour the extension of communication coverage in emergency situations.	OP4.2-2: Extend network coverage. OP4.2-4: Use of technologies that favour the extension of coverage to devices with fewer resources. OP4.2-5: Use of mobile technologies to facilitate service delivery. OP4.2-6: Use of UAVs for coverage extension in areas of difficult access or poor coverage. OP4.2-19: Extend IOT data range. OP4.2-22: Increase RF area coverage.
CO.WP4.8: Creation of communication preference mechanisms in the networks available during the emergency.	OP4.2-9: Creation of communication preference mechanisms in the networks available during the emergency.
CO.WP4.9: Use of regulations and communications technologies that ensure data privacy and security during data sharing. There is also an opportunity for implementing better control access mechanisms during data sharing.	OP4.2-10 Unified regulations for data protection in emergency scenarios OP4.2-11 Use of monitoring technologies or services capable of detecting threats that may affect the network. OP4.2-13 Use of technologies based on security constraints. OP.4.2-34 Shared Health data OP4.2-36 Light cryptographic protocols OP4.2-37 RBAC/ABAC OP4.2-39 Access limitation. OP4.5-23 Pseudonymisation. OP4.3-31 CEN TR 15872:2014 OP4.3-32 CEN TR 15299:2006
CO.WP4.10: Use of guidelines and protocols to provide data backup.	OP4.2-14: Definition of backup guidelines at EU level. OP4.2-15: Creation of data restoration contingency plans. OP4.2-16: Deployment of redundant services to provide back-up support in case of failure. OP4.2-30: Data Backup. OP4.2-33: Data backup servers.
CO.WP4.11: Structured management of information coming from different sources.	OP4.2-35: Querying data. OP4.2-38: Sectorization.
CO.WP4.12: Definition of standards regarding user devices specifications and their usage	OP4.2-40 Specific terminals for disasters OP4.2-41 Standard training in device use OP4.2-42 Standard capabilities of emergency devices
CO.WP4.13: VR debriefing systems.	OP4.3-1: VR debriefing systems.
CO.WP4.14: Multiplatform. Run different OS.	OP4.3-2: Multiplatform. Run different OS.
CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles.	OP4.3-3: Location of near/nearest vehicles.

Opportunities	Merged opportunities
CO.WP4.16: Georeferenced recording of events on the ground.	OP4.3-4: Georeferenced recording of events on the ground.
CO.WP4.17: HUMS (Health and Usage Monitoring Systems) or simulators for boosting forces.	OP4.3-6: HUMS (Health and Usage Monitoring Systems) or simulators for boosting forces.
CO.WP4.18: COP standardisation.	OP4.3-5: COP standardisation.
CO.WP4.19: Asset's responsiveness and being able to adapt to fast-changing environments, mission needs and scenarios.	OP4.3-7: Asset's responsiveness and being able to adapt to fast-changing environments, mission needs and scenarios.
CO.WP4.20: Detecting trends and achieving maximum operative readiness.	OP4.3-8: Detecting trends and achieving maximum operative readiness.
CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms.	OP4.3-9: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms.
CO.WP4.22: Social Network data visualization C2.	OP4.3-10: Social Network data visualization C2.
CO.WP4.23: Open Source C2 App.	OP4.3-11: Open Source C2 App.
CO.WP4.24: Satellite weather data recorded in Hybrid Digital Twins as a layer.	OP4.3-12: Satellite weather data recorded in Hybrid Digital Twins as a layer.
CO.WP4.25: Common Operational Picture exchange.	OP4.3-13: Common Operational Picture exchange.
CO.WP4.26: Guidelines for social media crawling	OP4.3-14 Guidelines for social media crawling. OP4.3-15 Guidelines for selecting social media crawling tools.
CO.WP4.27: Airspace coordination with drones.	OP4.3-18: Airspace coordination with drones.
CO.WP4.28: Cross border data trace.	OP4.3-20: Cross border data trace.
CO.WP4.29: Victims advance information.	OP4.3-21: Victims advance information.
CO.WP4.30: Victims' historical data.	OP4.3-22: Victims' historical data
CO.WP4.31: External data.	OP4.3-24: External data.
CO.WP4.32: Guidelines for identifying dangerous zones.	OP4.3-25: Guidelines for identifying dangerous zones.
CO.WP4.33: Identification of relevant locations.	OP4.3-26: Identification of relevant locations.

Opportunities	Merged opportunities
CO.WP4.34: Use of decision-making applications using AI-based systems.	OP4.3-27: Use of decision-making applications. OP4.4-13: Use of AI-based systems.
CO.WP4.35: Creation of operating procedures.	OP4.3-28: Creation of operating procedures.
CO.WP4.36: Incorporation of new standards.	OP4.3-29: Incorporation of new standards.
CO.WP4.37: EDXL HAVE Standard.	OP4.3-30: EDXL HAVE Standard.
CO.WP4.38: Digital Skills Improvement.	OP4.4-1: Digital Skills Improvement.
CO.WP4.39: European Iconographic Standardisation.	OP4.4-3: European Iconographic Standardisation.
CO.WP4.40: European data standardisation.	OP4.4-4: European data standardisation.
CO.WP4.41: Device's upgrade.	OP4.4-5: Device's upgrade.
CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges.	OP4.4-14: Reduce voice communication. OP4.4-15: Reduce digital workload.
CO.WP4.43: Placing FR as an important focus on the design of solutions.	OP4.4-16: Placing FR as an important focus on the design of solutions.
CO.WP4.44: Instant access with transparency to Crucial information in a secure way.	OP4.4-17: Instant access with transparency to Crucial information in a secure way.
CO.WP4.45: Best practice for introducing the e-tools where it is missing.	OP4.4-18: Best practice for introducing the e-tools where it is missing.
CO.WP4.46: Use of wearables to obtain information about patients and first responders, about the environment, and manage alerts.	OP4.2-20 Victims and FR data gathering. OP4.1-3: Tracking of personnel, equipment, and casualties. OP4.5-1: Use of wearables for tracking. OP4.5-2: Use of wearables for tracking. OP4.5-3: Use of wireless technologies in wearables. OP4.5-4: Use of RFID-based wearables for identification. OP4.5-5: NFC printing on traditional cards for identification. OP4.5-12: Warning of a danger for FRs. OP4.5-13: Automatic transmission of vital signs of FRs OP4.5-15: Broadcasting of safety and security information. OP4.5-16: Create common procedures for disaster fatality identification between different countries. OP4.5-17: Freezing the scene of a deceased victim discovery. OP4.5-18: Acquire unique IDs of implanted wearables. OP4.5-20: Use of first responder's telecom devices to record victim's data as per its wearable unique id.

Opportunities	Merged opportunities
	OP4.5-21: Collect victim's vital signs. OP4.5-22: Monitor patient vital signs. OP4.5-25: Victim's vital signs on route. OP4.5-26: Victim ID. OP4.4-2: Wearable's implementation. OP4.3-23: Traceability of victims and FR.
CO.WP4.47: Creation of wearable prototypes using own technologies.	OP4.5-6: Prototyping with own technologies. OP4.5-7: Firmware prototyping.
CO.WP4.48: Strategies for battery saving in wearables.	OP4.5-8: Adaptive data delivery. OP4.5-9: RFID to avoid batteries.
CO.WP4.49: Novel communication system between first responders using wearables.	OP4.5-10: Communicate by voice. OP4.5-11: Communication by text.
CO.WP4.50: Patient vital signs management and interoperability for healthcare.	OP4.5-24: Patient vital signs management and interoperability for healthcare.
CO.WP4.51: Define a telemedicine service during emergency actuations.	OP4.5-27: Telemedicine service. OP4.5-28: Telemedicine guidance. OP4.5-29: Telemedicine data collection.
CO.WP4.52: European Health Data Space	OP4.5-30: European Health Data Space
CO.WP4.53: Use of wearables on critically ill patients	OP4.5-31: Use of wearables on critically ill patients
CO.WP4.54: Manufacturing wearables according to medical regulations	OP4.5-32: Manufacturing wearables according to medical regulations.
CO.WP4.55: Use of wearables to support triage.	OP4.5-33: Use of wearables to support triage.
CO.WP4.56: Technology update business services model.	OP4.5-34: Technology update business services model.

Table 3 - WP4 opportunities after the clustering.

6. Opportunities analysis

6.1. Methodology (common)

It has been necessary to agree on the most relevant opportunities in the work packages. The following approach was commonly agreed upon and used in the opportunities analysis among the WP4, WP5 and WP6 opportunities and partners. A modified Delphi methodology has been used in which the experts are the consortium partners to reach this agreement.

The questionnaire consists of a score from 1 to 10 on 13 questions divided into two groups, feasibility and impact. The questions within the feasibility group focus on defining how feasible it is to implement the grouped opportunity. Aspects such as the resources or capacities of the system, ethical-legal regulation, technological advances, and implementation costs have been considered.

Feasibility determining factors evaluated	Contribution
Do the required training and learning processes present a high complexity to be implemented/operated?	8%
Is it possible to achieve a full operational harmonization for opportunities in less than a year for a first responder?	17%
Are there more than three first responders or entities involved to operate, consume or use directly this harmonization opportunity?	17%
Is there technology available to fulfill this opportunity?	17%
In terms of budget, how costly is it to develop, implement or operate this opportunity?	17%
How easy to implement in terms of legislation, ethics, and human rights?	7%
How easy is to verify and validate this opportunity in the whole Valkyries proposal?	17%

Table 4 - Questions related to the feasibility of the opportunities.

The questions within the impact group are focused on defining what the impact of the opportunity would be once implemented. Aspects such as the objective and the target stakeholders for whom it is proposed or what is expected to happen in the end must be considered.

Impact determining factors evaluated	
Is there any environmental/social impact/risk when deploying?	33%
How reusable is across different regions, actors, and scenarios?	14%
Does the impact expected save lives or reduce casualties directly?	14%
Does the expected impact reduce the time to act?	13%
Does the expected impact reduce the risk of mistakes or rework?	13%
Is the expected impact useful to learn for next actuaciones?	13%

Table 5 - Questions related to the impact of the opportunities.

With the answers to the questions and the appropriate weighting, a score will be obtained for each group, one for feasibility and one for impact. In this way, the opportunity can be placed in a matrix format.

The scores have been used as coordinates that replace the opportunity and locate the opportunity in the matrix. This can identify the opportunities with the best relation.

The result of the analysis in each case would fall into one of the following four combinations:

- **Low feasibility / Low impact (THANKLESS TASKS):** These initiatives are low recommended because they will not be significant for the desired changes in the system. The realisation of these initiatives involves a high degree of difficulty for the implementation, and the result will not significantly improve.
- **High feasibility / Low impact (FILL-INS):** These initiatives can be implemented quickly and in the short term, but their effect on the desired changes will be marginal and insignificant.
- **Low feasibility / High impact (MAJOR PROJETS):** These ideas, often disruptive, are complex to execute. They may require further analysis or follow-up to assess their priority, degree of impact, risks involved in implementing them (or not implementing them), etc.
- **High feasibility / High impact (QUICK WINS):** These initiatives can be implemented and executed relatively quickly in a short time. They are very valuable because they can significantly change the system.

The feasibility-impact matrix presents the results of the opportunities analysed in a scatter plot where each of the four combinations described corresponds to one of the four quadrants represented.

Figure 1 - Example of a feasibility-impact matrix.

6.2. Opportunities rating according to the questionnaire

The rate of each meta-opportunity was obtained from the answers given in the questionnaire by each partner in the VALKYRIES consortium. The results of each meta-opportunity, both its feasibility and its impact, are analysed below.

CO.WP4.1: Up to date information about the environment, detecting imminent risks for patients and first responders.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	Although it could be partially reusable in different regions, actors, and scenarios and could even contribute to less harm to victims and more safety for first responders, it is considered to have a very low impact on the rest of the evaluated items, especially about the expected impact useful for learning for future actions.	Although not in absolute terms, the feasibility of updating information on the environment and detection of imminent risks to patients and first responders, in relative terms is somewhat better. There would be some interest among stakeholders, and the difficulties of adoption are not so much in terms of training or technological support but perhaps in terms of the financial cost.
Rating	6,34	5,83

Table 6 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.1: Up to date information about the environment, detecting imminent risks for patients and first responders.

CO.WP4.2: Logistics assistance using UAVs.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	UAVs will reduce the time the first responders have to wait for the arrival of vital equipment. UAVs can quickly deliver this from the central logistic bases to the first responders in the casualties' areas. The UAV can also deliver equipment to casualties before the first responders arrive. This will reduce the time casualties must wait for assistance.	Several UAVs on the market build exist to take parcels between different locations. These UAVs come in different sizes regarding payload. One challenge is the prize issue and the training and certification of the operators.
Rating	7,07	6,63

Table 7 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.2: Logistics assistance using UAVs.

CO.WP4.3: Conduct search and relief missions.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	UAVs can cover large land and sea areas to look for both impacts from disasters and casualties. With various sensors, they can pinpoint how the disaster develops (for a forest fire or an oil spill). They will also locate persons in the disaster area and interact with them.	First responders already use UAVs for this purpose, but it has yet to be in everyday use. Making them autonomous using swarm theories will significantly increase the searched area and the frequency of visits to the same area.
Rating	7,28	5,55

Table 8 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.3: Conduct search and relief missions.

CO.WP4.4: Use of communication systems able to provide alternative communication capabilities, being also compatible with existing communication technologies using gateways.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	It will improve connectivity, support different network integration, provide more flexibility, and reduce evolution costs. It also enables more dynamic communication between FR and, by combining different communication alternatives, enables a wider communication coverage. It also supports legacy systems.	Difficult to obtain a high degree of reliability and to manage the technical differences between networks: latency, data rates, etc. Which required managing and prioritizing data for different purposes, which is a complex task. Managing the data flow between technology with different validation and transport protocols raises some complex challenges.
Rating	7,17	5,07

Table 9- Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.4: Use of communication systems able to provide alternative communication capabilities, being also compatible with existing communication technologies using gateways.

CO.WP4.5: Use of technologies that allow the adaptability of the network architecture, ensuring data availability.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	This opportunity has potential benefits, such as increased availability to ensure critical data is always accessible to those who need it. Another benefit is improved performance to optimize data transfer speeds and reduce latency. An additional advantage is a greater flexibility to allow network adaptability. The last benefit is enhanced security compared to traditional network management.	Software Defined Network (SDN) technology is mature, but the implementation is highly complex because the systems are very varied and specific developments would have to be made for each deployment. On the other hand, there is currently no regulation.
Rating	6,34	5,63

Table 10 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.5: Use of technologies that allow the adaptability of the network architecture, ensuring data availability.

CO.WP4.6: Selection of technologies based on the type of data to be transmitted.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	This opportunity can significantly impact the effectiveness and efficiency of the data transmission process. In addition, this can result in faster transmission times,	Feasibility is reduced because integrations between different technologies would have to be made. These integrations are not implemented today. Therefore, this opportunity would require an effort between

Doc title: Roadmap for enhancing the pan-European technological capabilities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters

	lower error rates, and a more reliable data transfer process.	technology developers, communication operators, etc.
Rating	6,07	5,62

Table 11 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.6: Selection of technologies based on the type of data to be transmitted.

CO.WP4.7: Use of technologies and guidelines that favour the extension of communication coverage in emergency situations.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	Communication is essential for coordinating and deploying rescue and relief efforts during emergencies. Technologies that can help extend communication coverage can provide coverage in areas where traditional communication networks may be disrupted or overloaded. Guidelines help ensure communication infrastructure is designed and deployed with emergencies in mind. Using these technologies and guidelines can afford faster response times, reduce the impact of disasters, and improve the overall effectiveness of emergency response efforts.	From a technological perspective, ad-hoc technologies would be needed for each situation, and it is not easy to have a single technology to extend coverage. On the other hand, there is currently no regulation, so it is a challenge for everyone to do it in a unified way.
Rating	6,47	5,42

Table 12 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.7: Use of technologies and guidelines that favour the extension of communication coverage in emergency situations.

CO.WP4.8: Creation of communication preference mechanisms in the networks available during the emergency.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	During an emergency, communication networks may become overloaded. Emergency responders can ensure that critical communication is given priority by creating communication preference mechanisms, such as prioritization of certain types of communication or users. Furthermore, these mechanisms can help individuals affected by an	There needs to be precise regulation on which technologies should be used before others.

Doc title: Roadmap for enhancing the pan-European technological capabilities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters

	emergency communication with each other and emergency responders.	
Rating	6,41	4,83

Table 13 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.8: Creation of communication preference mechanisms in the networks available during the emergency.

CO.WP4.9: Use of regulations and communications technologies that ensure data privacy and security during data sharing. There is also an opportunity for implementing better control access mechanisms during data sharing.

	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	Some potential impacts are: the protection of personal information, prevention of data breaches by ensuring that data is secure and protected, emergency responders can minimize the risk of breaches and prevent potentially harmful consequences, and facilitation of effective communication, to ensure that everyone has access to the information they need to make informed decisions and take appropriate actions.	All technologies guarantee privacy and data security, but the problem is that their use could be more widespread, and even the application of these mechanisms will depend on the scenario to be performed. Therefore, extending it to the whole EU is a significant challenge.
Rating	5,87	5,55

Table 14 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.9: Use of regulations and communications technologies that ensure data privacy and security during data sharing. There is also an opportunity for implementing better control access mechanisms during data sharing.

CO.WP4.10: Use of guidelines and protocols to provide data backup.

	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	Providing needed data to first responders and supporting their activities through technical and technological tools will improve the effectiveness of their work. The availability is the critical feature of data. Using guidelines and protocols as pre-standardisation procedures will be beneficial for harmonizing the solutions for data backup of all partners and guaranteeing the effectiveness of the emergency response and rescue operations.	Harmonising the use of guidelines and protocols for data backup to support first responders in multi-casualty incidents will take longer than the project timeframe. It would be possible to define some common guidelines for data backup as a pre-harmonisation activity.

Doc title: Roadmap for enhancing the pan-European technological capabilities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters

Rating	5,67	6,16
--------	------	------

Table 15 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.10: Use of guidelines and protocols to provide data backup.

CO.WP4.11: Structured management of information coming from different sources.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	The technological revolution regarding the possibilities to gather data has made the information flow for command and control so high that it hampers situational awareness and increases the risk of information overload. One important asset that will help is the possibility of having all the information presented in one system with one common language.	There are systems where multiple sources of information can be presented as one, but with limitations. Current work focuses on several systems to make it easier to connect sources regardless of language, software, and protocols. And at the same time, it keeps the usability as easy and intuitive as possible to reduce the need for too much training of the first responders.
Rating	6,25	5,94

Table 16 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.11: Structured management of information coming from different sources.

CO.WP4.12: Definition of standards regarding user devices specifications and their usage.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	The score of this opportunity standards suggests that it could have some impact. However, defining standards could help ensure that devices are compatible with each other, but the effects may be limited as device specifications are constantly evolving. In addition, standards can be costly and challenging to implement in the industry, especially if there is resistance from device manufacturers.	The definition of standards is a long process since, first, it is necessary to analyse the literature in depth to implement a valid solution, being higher than the time of the VALKYRIES Project. Moreover, these standards need to be learned by FRs despite needing to gain experience with devices.
Rating	5,94	5,24

Table 17 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.12: Definition of standards regarding user devices specifications and their usage.

CO.WP4.13: VR debriefing systems.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	Overall, VR technology can improve C2 team training and performance by providing a more realistic, objective, and safer training experience:	Implementation of VR systems in C2 is becoming more feasible due to technological advances and decreasing equipment and software costs.

Doc title: Roadmap for enhancing the pan-European technological capabilities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters

	simulation of complex environments, objective performance assessment, decision-making assessment under pressure, improved collaboration, and cost and risk reduction associated with training.	However, there are still challenges and limitations before it can be fully integrated into C2 operations: Technical limitations in the quality and capacity of VR systems, costs can still be expensive, integration in C2 systems can be challenging, and the change in the adoption of new technologies in the organizational culture and the mindset of operators.
Rating	6,00	5,07

Table 18 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.13: VR debriefing systems.

CO.WP4.14: Multiplatform. Run different OS.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	By supporting multiple OS and platforms, the solution becomes more agnostic of the technology, leading to the capacity to integrate more users and increasing flexibility and resilience.	Several functions can be virtualized and could quickly provide a cross-platform cross-OS functional capability. The maintenance of the solution and the performance could be impacted. But, overall, it can be feasible to incorporate cross OS/platforms, middleware, etc.
Rating	5,53	5,99

Table 19 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.14: Multiplatform. Run different OS.

CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	The ability to collect and disseminate the location of the near assets is a significant gain in improving the response time of emergency operations, which can reduce the victim numbers.	Relatively easy nowadays, technology chain is available and robust: GNSS receiver (Galileo or GPS) + digital communications of mobile network (4G/5G, WiFi, etc.) and data model is well known. The challenge remains in the coherence and integration of the data model used for data interoperability between different tools and users.
Rating	7,04	7,13

Table 20 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles

CO.WP4.16: Georeferenced recording of events on the ground.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	The georeferencing and recording of the ground event increase the ability to have a tactical picture of the actors in the operations field, better manage and coordinate actions, and combine response capabilities.	Relatively easy nowadays if network connectivity is available to report the vehicles and victim's position.
Rating	6,61	7,00

Table 21 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.16: Georeferenced recording of events on the ground.

CO.WP4.17: HUMS (Health and Usage Monitoring Systems) or simulators for boosting forces.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	<p>In managing an emergency where it is necessary to deploy a high volume of devices and vehicles, the vehicles and devices to be used must be safely assured.</p> <p>In this sense, monitoring equipment status and ensuring effective maintenance is vital to incident management. Using HUMS technologies reduces mission cancellations and maintenance costs and directly impacts incident management and the FRs' sense of safety.</p>	<p>Electronic devices and control systems increasingly have technical signals that allow them to be monitored in real-time. In addition to this online monitoring, the availability of digitalised data allows predictive algorithms to be applied to determine the possible points of failure of the elements. In any case, the first step is to have sensors in the vehicles (geolocation sensors, wearables, or devices used by the FR itself) that generate this information, centralise these data and be able to apply algorithms to analyse these data.</p>
Rating	6,21	5,77

Table 22 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.17: HUMS (Health and Usage Monitoring Systems) or simulators for boosting forces.

CO.WP4.18: COP standardisation.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	<p>COP standardisation can improve the efficiency and effectiveness of emergency response by reducing the time and effort required to collect and share information. This can result in better utilization of resources and a faster and more effective response to the emergency.</p> <p>Standardisation can facilitate interoperability between information systems used by different organizations. For example, Geographic Information Systems (GIS) can be standardized to allow information integration from different sources and systems.</p>	<p>COP standardisation can be a challenging process, as it involves integrating different information systems and cooperating with multiple organizations and government agencies.</p> <p>However, there are several efforts underway to standardize the COP. For example, NATO has developed a standard called Standardisation Agreement (STANAG) 4609 which establishes requirements for exchanging geospatial information and developing COPs for military operations. There is a project of the European Union called Common information space in the civil sphere to establish a common framework for emergency management.</p>
Rating	6,75	6,04

Table 23 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.18: COP standardisation.

CO.WP4.19: Asset's responsiveness and being able to adapt to fast-changing environments, mission needs and scenarios.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	The ability to adapt rapidly to fast-changing conditions is critical in emergencies. Emergency responders need to be able to adjust quickly to new information and changing circumstances to ensure that they are responding appropriately and effectively. For example, emergency responders may need to deploy specialized equipment or technology to address a specific emergency. Therefore, personnel needs to be trained and equipped. This may include changing response plans, adjusting resource allocation, or altering.	Adapting technologically to rapidly changing scenarios is challenging and requires using technologies still being explored, such as AI or SDN.
Rating	6,14	5,18

Table 24 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.19: Asset's responsiveness and being able to adapt to fast-changing environments, mission needs and scenarios.

CO.WP4.20: Detecting trends and achieving maximum operative readiness.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	Use of logged data exchanged and recorded/secured/stamped with Blockchain technologies to analyse the performance of systems and workflows after the incident	According to WP5 analysis of similar clustered opportunities, such a method, as a standard, will have a positive impact on the harmonization and standardisation path of plans, acting as the technological background
Rating	6,07	5,39

Table 25 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.20: Detecting trends and achieving maximum operative readiness.

CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	This analysis can help to identify patterns, trends, and areas for improvement, which can inform future decision-making and planning. In	As we start from existing data, it does not matter what the application scenario or the technologies used, as we want to generate datasets and statistical tests from these

CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms.		
	addition, this analysis can also be used to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of future emergency response efforts. By analysing past incidents and responses, organizations can identify areas for improvement, such as better resource allocation or more effective communication.	existing data to ensure that they can be used with AI at a later stage.
Rating	6,99	6,75

Table 26 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms.

CO.WP4.22: Social Network data visualization C2.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	This opportunity can provide emergency responders with real-time information about the situation on the ground, such as the location of people in need, the status of critical infrastructure, or the scope of the emergency. On the other hand, this opportunity can also help improve coordination among agencies and stakeholders involved in emergency response efforts.	It is not easy to obtain information from social networks to represent the current situation and be included in current C2 systems.
Rating	6,60	4,96

Table 27 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.22: Social Network data visualization C2.

CO.WP4.23: Open Source C2 App.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	The implementation of Open-Source solutions for C2 operations can have several significant impacts on the efficiency, flexibility, and security of operations: reduced costs, solutions highly customizable and modular, accessibility or available to everyone,	Although open source C2 solutions have been available for several decades, it has only been in recent years that their use has increased significantly due to the increased availability and acceptance of open-source technologies in the military and government industry. Many open-source C2 solutions are available today, such as ATAK, OpenTAK, Ushahidi, SAHANA, and EpiCollect+. These solutions have proven helpful for various applications,

CO.WP4.23: Open Source C2 App.		
	transparency, and a greater community which can drive innovation, continuous improvement, and security testing to ensure the integrity of their systems.	from disaster management to military operations. Implementing Open-Source solutions may also require a greater customization and training effort than proprietary solutions.
Rating	6,26	5,76

Table 28 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.23: Open Source C2 App.

CO.WP4.24: Satellite weather data recorded in Hybrid Digital Twins as a layer.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	Having weather and forecast information available at the time of the incident can facilitate decision-making. The fact that forecasts use different standards and methodologies can complicate in-country decision making and cross-border incident management.	The registration of this weather forecast data, through available APIs, from ESA and/or NASA and/or ARATOS satellite systems can solve the gap by exchanging tactical information COPS between Agencies and countries by sharing the registered data from the Hybrid Digital Twins.
Rating	6,13	5,75

Table 29 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.24: Satellite weather data recorded in Hybrid Digital Twins as a layer.

CO.WP4.25: Common Operational Picture exchange.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	Situational awareness and a common operational picture among different agencies engaged in response to multi-casualty incidents are one of the most crucial aspects for managing disasters and crises. Through the quick and effective exchange of information between FRs, efficiency and speed in the response operations can be achieved, thus increasing the manageability of the situation, reducing response times, and, consequently, providing proper and timely first aid to victims.	Today there is a variety of tools that have been developed to provide a common operational picture to the stakeholders engaged in managing a disaster. On the other hand, the use of different tools by different organisations might have the opposite effect, i.e., each organisation has a different level of situational awareness. There is a need for a common and mutual understanding of the situation. The harmonisation-federation of such COP-providing systems could be the answer to the solution to this problem.
Rating	6,86	5,65

Table 30 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.25: Common Operational Picture exchange.

CO.WP4.26: Guidelines for social media crawling.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	During emergency responses, social media can provide valuable information that can help FRs and other emergency personnel quickly and accurately assess the situation, identify areas of need, and coordinate response efforts. Furthermore, these guidelines can help ensure that social media data is collected and used in a responsible and effective manner.	Each social network defines its own mechanisms and restrictions for data acquisition; therefore, it is difficult to establish a common form for all social networks. In addition, information on social media can be erroneous or incomplete, making it difficult to be accurate. With so many data sources, it is difficult to integrate them.
Rating	6,31	5,52

Table 31 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.26: Guidelines for social media crawling.

CO.WP4.27: Airspace coordination with drones.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	The use of drones, especially UAV has exploded in the recent years commercial, public, and private. This resulted in several incidents where drones have interfered with aircraft and helicopter operations in disaster relief operations. To let the airspace coordination systems (air traffic control) also include UAVs will increase the safety for all flying vehicles, but also increase the efficiency of UAVs operations.	The organizational system exists in the existing airspace management coordination. The challenges are connecting all the different UAV operators into it and making a minimum competence level for them, so they know the possibilities, limitations, and procedures to follow. This ensures the efficient use of UAVs within the existing airspace management systems without complex procedures hampering their usability.
Rating	6,87	5,22

Table 32 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.27: Airspace coordination with drones.

CO.WP4.28: Cross border data trace.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	Data exchanged between federated systems, following the SINGRUN architecture, in COP that can be exchanged	As SINGRUN architecture has been designed to offer such functionality as well as bi-lateral agreements on data exchange between countries, a clear path for a

CO.WP4.28: Cross border data trace.		
	between neighbor Civil Protection Agencies engaged in cross-border incidents, being feasible following the defined standards of the VALKYRIES Project.	standardisation/harmonization opportunity to define a new EU standard is open.
Rating	7,41	6,67

Table 33 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.28: Cross border data trace.

CO.WP4.29: Victims advance information.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	The ability to share victim data with the target medical facility would allow them to prepare to receive a patient with certain characteristics. Continuous monitoring of vital parameters during transport would also ensure rapid response to changes in status and the capability by medical personnel to guide responders in corrective actions	Real-time sharing of an MCI victim's clinical condition between different parties is very complicated outside of a common platform. In addition, the transmission of information must be secure and visible only to the defined recipients. With this in mind, the SIGRUN architecture could be an effective solution considering, however, the difficulties associated with its deployment
Rating	7,67	5,95

Table 34 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.29: Victims advance information.

CO.WP4.30: Victims' historical data.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	Victims' minimum data sets (those needed hospitalization and others due to the execution of evacuation plans) are recorded and secured against any GDPR related violation due to the SINGRUN architecture.	Precise and secure tracking of victims during and after the disaster, primarily if this functionality is supported with wearables track&trace devices. The impact is evident as no standard for non-needed-hospitalization victims is in force today, all-around EU.
Rating	6,67	6,08

Table 35 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.30: Victims' historical data.

CO.WP4.31: External data.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	Emergency response teams often rely on a wide range of data to make critical decisions quickly and effectively, and external data sources can	As the data is already existing and possibly structured, we would need to use mechanisms to adapt the data to our platform. However, there may be platforms that make it very difficult to obtain the data,

CO.WP4.31: External data.		
	provide valuable information that may not be available from internal sources.	so even if the data is easy to integrate across platforms, there may be difficulties in obtaining the data.
Rating	5,94	6,68

Table 36 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.31: External data.

CO.WP4.32: Guidelines for identifying dangerous zones.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	Emergency response and emergency planning can be made in tandem, between bordering countries, where dangerous zones are typified according to geographical, meteorological and population density factors, among others. As such, this would facilitate crisis response and solution rollouts, saving time and streamlining agents' responses (Healthcare professionals, Police, Civil Protection, Firefighters, etc) from both sides of the border.	Several existing protocols between neighbouring countries facilitate this, and systems are in place to guarantee its execution. Guidelines should be homogenous in both countries and understandable from all sides of the emergency response operation.
Rating	6,41	6,65

Table 37 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.32: Guidelines for identifying dangerous zones.

CO.WP4.33: Identification of relevant locations.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	It can have several positive impacts on improving coordination in cross-border crises, reducing response time, making faster and more effective decisions, improving resource management, increase citizen safety and the efficiency of emergency services in different countries.	EU has developed a standard to share the definition of relevant positions called Common Emergency Communication and Information System (CECIS) that uses a standardized data format to describe the location and nature of emergencies, allowing different emergency services to work together more effectively. The level of implementation varies among the countries of the EU. Its adoption and use depend on several factors: available infrastructure, technical capacity, and financial resources.
Rating	6,61	6,59

Table 38 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.33: Identification of relevant locations.

CO.WP4.34: Use of decision-making applications using AI-based systems.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	AI-based systems can analyse large amounts of data from various sources to identify areas of need and assess the situation quickly. This can help FRs make more informed decisions faster and with greater accuracy. In addition, these systems can also help emergency responders allocate resources more effectively and help identify potential risks and hazards in emergencies to take preventive measures to minimize the impact of disasters.	Although AI is mature and can make decisions, the fact that it is applied in such a complex and changing scenario with many possible decisions makes it difficult to use in emergency situations.
Rating	5,59	4,56

Table 39 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.34: Use of decision-making applications using AI-based systems.

CO.WP4.35: Creation of operating procedures.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	International standards evolve with the market to guarantee its quality and the use it has been designed. It is considered of high interest to identify in the operating procedures the requirements that the different equipment and devices must meet concerning their associated technology.	It is considered complicated to generate operational procedures considering all the possible technologies in use and at the forefront inherently represented in each device and equipment while considering the influence of the country of origin and use.
Rating	6,20	4,92

Table 40 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.35: Creation of operating procedures.

CO.WP4.36: Incorporation of new standards.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	The standards are continuously updated to safeguard the safe use of equipment and equipment by people and their environment, this also	All the information and data related to managing cross-border emergencies must consider all the known risks and apply all the necessary security measures to address technological advances and their associated risks. The standards are reviewed for the use

CO.WP4.36: Incorporation of new standards.		
	contemplates the use of information and data, whatever its nature.	of proactive tools according to an ongoing risk assessment.
Rating	6,61	6,93

Table 41 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.36: Incorporation of new standards.

CO.WP4.37: EDXL HAVE Standard.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	The EDXL standard allows the exchange of information about hospital capacities. This allows optimization of resource management in emergency management.	EDX allows the exchange of information between different organizations and entities related to emergency management, improving the standardisation of communications, and consequently improving the results of interventions.
Rating	6,61	6,17

Table 42 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.37: EDXL HAVE Standard.

CO.WP4.38: Digital Skills Improvement.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	Nowadays, each first responder needs to be skilled in using technology to simplify and shorten the time for response. Digital literacy needs to be improved regarding the plans such as the "European Sills Agenda" of the EC. Digital literacy will ensure the proper use of new devices and provide more information during the emergency situations.	First responders operate with various technology, which requires various devices. Since many devices used nowadays are outdated and not updated regularly, the difficulty of improving digital skills is more challenging to reach in a short time horizon.
Rating	6,67	5,85

Table 43 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.38: Digital Skills Improvement.

CO.WP4.39: European Iconographic Standardisation.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	In order to overcome language barriers, the use of icons and symbols may facilitate to promptly understand the meaning of messages and information.	Technical language is universal, therefore, to extract common icons and symbols shouldn't be too difficult also considering the ISO/IEC 11581-40:2011 purposes (6).
Rating	5,99	6,00

Table 44 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.39: European Iconographic Standardisation.

CO.WP4.40: European data standardisation.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	To standardise the flows under a minimum dataset to efficiently manage disasters could strongly improve the level of accountability in the sector	Categories of data are already set from articles 6 (7) and 9 (8) GDPR, therefore once the legal basis and the means of data processing are set, it wouldn't be difficult to select by design how to manage data.
Rating	6,53	6,36

Table 45 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.40: European data standardisation.

CO.WP4.41: Device's upgrade.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	This opportunity required that all devices used and involved during first aid actuations and specifically during MCI accomplish the required computational and graphical requirements, and those devices should be evaluated and upgraded regularly. If these requirements are fulfilled, then this should make the work of first responders more effective, faster, and reduce time.	Device upgrade means that all devices used by various first responders during emergency response need regular actuations and upgrades. Hence this is a very urgent requirement, it is not feasible to harmonize. It is hard to implement in one country, not in more countries or within the EU. This requires much money and much time. This opportunity is not feasible to implement in the VALKYRIES project's timeframe.
Rating	6,83	5,34

Table 46 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.41: Device's upgrade.

CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	Reducing voice communications and the digital workload of users through the implementation of technological applications can improve efficiency in services (can spend more time and resources on emergencies), improve the accuracy and quality of information, increase citizen safety in disaster situations, can improve the efficiency, accuracy, and quality of	Reducing the number of phone calls is feasible using technologies and solutions that give people alternatives to communicate and get help in emergency situations. Some examples of processes that can be automated are monitoring and warning, automation of communications to improve coordination in emergency services, response and assistance that can guide to providing first aid, evacuation, search and rescue, collection, and analysis of data from sensors, cameras, and other devices to provide real-time information.

CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges.		
	information, reduce human error, and speed up response to natural disaster situations.	
Rating	7,34	6,70

Table 47 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges.

CO.WP4.43: Placing FR as an important focus on the design of solutions.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	This opportunity has received a relatively low impact score. The evaluators understood that these efforts would only sometimes be reusable in different regions, actors, and scenarios. Their favourable effect on reducing response times or errors was considered more likely, but their direct influence on saving lives needed to be considered evident.	Placing first responders at the centre of the design of solutions was seen as a second priority opportunity, albeit one of high feasibility. It facilitates appropriate design for the training of first responders because it is technologically affordable and because it is an approach understood to be key in the spirit of Valkyries, as shown by the composition of the project consortium.
Rating	6,13	6,25

Table 48 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.43: Placing FR as an important focus on the design of solutions.

CO.WP4.44: Instant access with transparency to Crucial information in a secure way.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	Easy access to crucial information in a timely and reliable (secure) manner via the implementation of technological solutions can speed up the process of responding to an emergency and this way to limit casualties. The correct and timely information will allow first responders to assess the situation adequately and perform the rescue operations accurately. This would be resulted in improving FR work.	Instant access to crucial information securely and reliably applying technological solutions is not easy to implement in the limited short time of the project and at the planned TRL of the technological tools. It is possible to implement some technical mechanisms for security, for instance, access control and authorization of the users who can access critical data.
Rating	6,97	6,17

Table 49 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.44: Instant access with transparency to Crucial information in a secure way.

CO.WP4.45: Best practice for introducing the e-tools where it is missing.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	The introduction of electronic tools to support the different actors or responsibilities in the different phases of the emergency was considered a priority in the upper-middle segment of the overall ranking of the opportunities analysed. It is considered that it cannot only make the work of first responders more efficient but also allow for a more accurate and detailed analysis of the actions to facilitate learning from mistakes and can ultimately have a positive impact on the final health outcomes of the victims.	The evaluators understand that technological development is currently favourable to establishing good practices for introducing e-tools where they do not exist but that the necessary training and learning processes would be more challenging to implement and operate. The costs involved in such an introduction and other aspects, such as legal issues, were of intermediate complexity, as was the overall assessment of this opportunity.
Rating	6,73	5,92

Table 50 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.45: Best practice for introducing the e-tools where it is missing.

CO.WP4.46: Use of wearables to obtain information about patients and first responders, about the environment, and manage alerts.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	Using wearables to obtain data from patients, non-patient victims, and first responders is crucial for triage applications and other tactical decision-making decisions during and after the catastrophic event. The communication technologies embedded in such wearables (or in cooperation with other communication devices) affect their uses according to the availability of terrestrial communication networks during a major catastrophic event.	As chipset technologies (NFC, IoT, Satellite IoT (SIoT), etc.) allow the use of cost-affordable technologies within wearables (including those on vehicles, machinery, etc.), geolocation, vital signs or data and emergency communications (“panic alerts”) from first responders are easy to introduce through existing products and applications.
Rating	6,33	5,92

Table 51 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.46: Use of wearables to obtain information about patients and first responders, about the environment, and manage alerts.

CO.WP4.47: Creation of wearable prototypes using own technologies.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	Existing products and services developed with IoT/blockchain technologies can quickly expand their functionality over SINGRUN minimum data set for 1. Recording and tracing a victim from Ground0 till the delivery to EMS 2. As an alternative triage solution, without any federated triage system 3. As a system to register, tag, and track&trace the status of victims that do not require hospitalization (internal refugees)	Existing commercial systems (NFC wearables, blockchain records of data and transactions) can be expanded through mobile apps to cover the needs and the impacts.
Rating	7,08	6,36

Table 52 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.47: Creation of wearable prototypes using own technologies.

CO.WP4.48: Strategies for battery saving in wearables.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	Nowadays, saving batteries in wearables during emergency response is vital since such devices decrease the time to act, for example, by monitoring the patients, for triage, etc. Consequently, wearables need to be always turned on.	Although the number of wearables whose battery is quite long, it is necessary to develop standards that allow saving battery of devices. This task could be challenging since first, the standards must be developed, and subsequently, FRs must know who implements them in real scenarios, causing the time for this opportunity is higher than the Valkyries project.
Rating	7,00	5,32

Table 53 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.48: Strategies for battery saving in wearables.

CO.WP4.49: Novel communication system between first responders using wearables.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	The idea of using wearables to improve communication between first responders in an emergency can have a significant impact on the effectiveness of emergency responses. Wearables can provide a faster and more efficient way for emergency	Wearables and communication technologies are widely available in the literature and can be used to improve communication between emergency teams. Communication technologies such as Bluetooth and Wi-Fi enable device connectivity and could be used to establish a communication network between emergency teams. However, issues

CO.WP4.49: Novel communication system between first responders using wearables.		
	responders to communicate and coordinate their actions, which could improve response time and reduce the risk of injury or loss of life.	such as interoperability, maintenance, and security must be considered.
Rating	6,47	7,13

Table 54 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.49: Novel communication system between first responders using wearables.

CO.WP4.50: Patient vital signs management and interoperability for healthcare.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	Even though vital signs management is crucial for triage applications and usually covered by the appropriate Triage management federated systems, first responders' vital signs, geolocation, and similar signs from emergency response vehicles and equipment could be critical for emergency plan execution.	The opportunity to harmonize vital signs both from victims and first responders on federated COPs creates a new path for advances both for existing systems based on terrestrial communications as well as for new systems based on EAS Copernicus Emergency Services based on satellite communications.
Rating	7,06	6,62

Table 55 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.50: Patient vital signs management and interoperability for healthcare.

CO.WP4.51: Define a telemedicine service during emergency actuations.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	This opportunity has been included in the medium-high segment of those analysed. As reasons for this, it is estimated that the work of medical care of victims outside the hospital would be favoured in terms of quality and speed, and therefore effectiveness. And this should have a direct impact on saving human lives in the context of MCIs or disasters.	The feasibility of this opportunity has been considered medium-low: although the technological development of telemedicine has kept pace with the times and now offers excellent options, the cost is still considered a negative constraint for its generalisation, and there are legal (e.g., professional competencies or data protection) and political aspects that reduce the possibility of increasing its degree of implementation in the context of disasters, even more so when these affect several countries at the same time.
Rating	7,30	5,76

Table 56 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.51: Define a telemedicine service during emergency actuations.

CO.WP4.52: European Health Data Space.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	In MCI, victims' health data can be complicated to retrieve, yet it is vital information. The opportunity to access the European Health Data Space ecosystem would allow, in full compliance with European privacy laws, emergency access to victims' medical history and sharing them among all health professionals involved.	The main critical issue is that the legislative process of the European Health Data Space will hopefully be completed by June 2024, and the aim is to have the EHDS up and running in 2025. Having done this, the implementation within architecture such as SIGRUN should be feasible.
Rating	6,80	5,76

Table 57 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.52: European Health Data Space.

CO.WP4.53: Use of wearables on critically ill patients.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	The use of wearables on patients and critically ill patients would allow healthcare professionals / first responders to monitor several patients. At the same time, they also continue their duties and responsibilities in mass casualty/emergency incidents, such as triage and guiding patients to safe zones, resulting in a faster workflow and guaranteeing that every patient with a wearable is being closely monitored (as this can be done by several people simultaneously).	The technology for such a method already exists, although its full potential is yet to be reached: mass monitoring, as well as data safely transmitted from place of occurrence – Hospital must be guaranteed, as to guarantee that no person or persons are left with wearables, but no monitoring. There is also room to argue that the wearables could be used during patient transportation. Finally, depending on how critically ill the patient is, or what the injuries are, the wearable might not be ideal for use.
Rating	7,40	5,72

Table 58 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.53: Use of wearables on critically ill patients.

CO.WP4.54: Manufacturing wearables according to medical regulations.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	Some of the problems related to the emergency use of wearable devices to detect vital parameters (heart rate, O2 saturation, etc.) are due to the uncertified measurement	It is likely to think that the production of devices in line with medical regulations could be a cost burden for manufacturers, however, it could be an opening to a larger market, not to mention that the Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and

CO.WP4.54: Manufacturing wearables according to medical regulations.		
	quality combined with the data's non-unique formatting. This could be remedied by certifying wearables as medical devices.	of the Council on the European Health Data Space provides for interoperability with medical devices
Rating	6,77	6,78

Table 59 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.54: Manufacturing wearables according to medical regulations.

CO.WP4.55: Use of wearables to support triage.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	The use of wearables (either with embedded telecommunication (terrestrial or satellite) capabilities or as passive tags activated with other available telecommunication devices) can introduce bettered harmonized procedures in triage procedures	As existing triage systems are activated by medical/paramedical personnel/first responders, using such wearables to initially tag/record a victim from "ground 0" of an accident by other first responders can increase the triage perimeter and decrease the loss of information. The SINGRUN blockchain recording general mechanism of exchanged data between federated systems is also the basis for executing GDPR compliance procedures.
Rating	7,53	6,37

Table 60 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.55: Use of wearables to support triage.

CO.WP4.56: Technology update business services model.		
	Impact	Feasibility
Explanation	As SINGRUN has been designed as an interconnection node of existing federated systems, any update (technological or procedural) of them following the same standard can keep them operational for much longer than usual.	The EU industry specialising in IT technologies can design better systems based on the standards introduced by the SINGRUN architecture/minimum data sets.
Rating	6,60	6,85

Table 61 - Impact and feasibility scores of the opportunity CO.WP4.56: Technology update business services model.

6.3. Opportunities matrix

Once all clustered opportunities have been assessed, these were fit in the feasibility-impact matrix according to its feasibility-impact score (see Figure 2). That figure shows that most opportunities fit in the "quick wins" quadrant. Furthermore, Figure 3 represents the same graph

as before, but in this case, it presents the six top-ranked opportunities that will be chosen subsequently to implement.

Figure 2 – WP4 clustered opportunities feasibility-impact matrix.

Figure 3 - WP4 clustered opportunities selecting the 6 top-ranked.

7. Opportunity ranking in WP4

Finally, to get the total score of each opportunity, its feasibility score and impact score have been added. Therefore, we can order the opportunities (see Table 62) according to their score.

Order	Cl. opp code	Opportunity	Feasibility	Impact	Total score
1º	CO.WP4.15	Location of near/nearest vehicles	7,13	7,04	14,17
2º	CO.WP4.28	Cross border data trace	6,67	7,41	14,08
3º	CO.WP4.42	Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges	6,70	7,34	14,04
4º	CO.WP4.55	Use of wearables to support triage	6,37	7,53	13,90
5º	CO.WP4.21	Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms	6,75	6,99	13,74
6º	CO.WP4.2	Logistics assistance using UAVs	6,63	7,07	13,70
7º	CO.WP4.50	Patient vital signs management and interoperability for healthcare	6,62	7,06	13,68
8º	CO.WP4.29	Victims advance information	5,95	7,67	13,62
9º	CO.WP4.16	Georeferenced recording of events on the ground	7,00	6,61	13,61
10º	CO.WP4.49	Novel communication system between first responders using wearables	7,13	6,47	13,60
11º	CO.WP4.54	Manufacturing wearables according to medical regulations	6,78	6,77	13,54
12º	CO.WP4.36	Incorporation of new standards	6,93	6,61	13,54
13º	CO.WP4.56	Technology update business services model	6,85	6,60	13,45
14º	CO.WP4.47	Creation of wearable prototypes using own technologies	6,36	7,08	13,43
15º	CO.WP4.33	Identification of relevant locations	6,59	6,61	13,19
16º	CO.WP4.52	European Health Data Space	5,76	6,80	13,16
17º	CO.WP4.44	Instant access with transparency to Crucial information in a secure way	6,17	6,97	13,13
18º	CO.WP4.32	Guidelines for identifying dangerous zones	6,65	6,41	13,06
19º	CO.WP4.51	Define a telemedicine service during emergency actuations	5,76	7,30	13,06
20º	CO.WP4.40	European data standardisation	6,36	6,53	12,89

Order	Cl. opp code	Opportunity	Feasibility	Impact	Total score
21º	CO.WP4.3	Conduct search and relief missions	5,55	7,28	12,83
22º	CO.WP4.18	COP standardisation	6,04	6,75	12,79
23º	CO.WP4.37	EDXL HAVE Standard	6,17	6,61	12,78
24º	CO.WP4.30	Victims' historical data	6,08	6,67	12,75
25º	CO.WP4.45	Best practice for introducing the e-tools where it is missing.	5,92	6,73	12,65
26º	CO.WP4.31	External data	6,68	5,94	12,62
27º	CO.WP4.38	Digital Skills Improvement	5,85	6,67	12,52
28º	CO.WP4.53	Use of wearables on critically ill patients	5,72	7,40	12,52
29º	CO.WP4.25	Common Operational Picture exchange	5,65	6,86	12,51
30º	CO.WP4.43	Placing FR as an important focus on the design of solutions	6,25	6,13	12,38
31º	CO.WP4.48	Strategies for battery saving in wearables	5,32	7,00	12,32
32º	CO.WP4.46	Use of wearables to obtain information about patients and first responders, about the environment, and manage alerts	5,92	6,33	12,25
33º	CO.WP4.4	Use of communication systems able to provide alternative communication capabilities, being also compatible with existing communication technologies using gateways	5,07	7,17	12,24
34º	CO.WP4.11	Structured management of information coming from different sources	5,94	6,25	12,19
35º	CO.WP4.41	Device's upgrade	5,34	6,83	12,17
36º	CO.WP4.1	Up to date information about the environment, detecting imminent risks for patients and first responders	5,83	6,34	12,17
37º	CO.WP4.27	Airspace coordination with drones	5,22	6,87	12,08
38º	CO.WP4.23	Open Source C2 App	5,76	6,26	12,02
39º	CO.WP4.39	European Iconographic Standardisation	6,00	5,99	11,99
40º	CO.WP4.17	HUMS (Health and Usage Monitoring Systems) or simulators for boosting forces	5,77	6,21	11,98

Order	Cl. opp code	Opportunity	Feasibility	Impact	Total score
41º	CO.WP4.5	Use of technologies that allow the adaptability of the network architecture, ensuring data availability	5,63	6,34	11,97
42º	CO.WP4.7	Use of technologies and guidelines that favour the extension of communication coverage in emergency situations	5,42	6,47	11,89
43º	CO.WP4.24	Satellite weather data recorded in Hybrid Digital Twins as a layer	5,75	6,13	11,88
44º	CO.WP4.10	Use of guidelines and protocols to provide data backup	6,16	5,67	11,83
45º	CO.WP4.26	Guidelines for social media crawling	5,52	6,31	11,83
46º	CO.WP4.6	Selection of technologies based on the type of data to be transmitted	5,62	6,07	11,69
47º	CO.WP4.22	Social Network data visualization C2	4,96	6,60	11,56
48º	CO.WP4.14	Multiplatform. Run different OS	5,99	5,53	11,52
49º	CO.WP4.20	Detecting trends and achieving maximum operative readiness	5,39	6,07	11,45
50º	CO.WP4.9	Use of regulations and communications technologies that ensure data privacy and security during data sharing. There is also an opportunity for implementing better control access mechanisms during data sharing.	5,55	5,87	11,42
51º	CO.WP4.19	Asset's responsiveness and being able to adapt to fast-changing environments, mission needs and scenarios	5,18	6,14	11,31
52º	CO.WP4.8	Creation of communication preference mechanisms in the networks available during the emergency	4,83	6,41	11,24
53º	CO.WP4.12	Definition of standards regarding user devices specifications and their usage	5,24	5,94	11,18
54º	CO.WP4.35	Creation of operating procedures	4,92	6,20	11,12
55º	CO.WP4.13	VR debriefing systems	5,07	6,00	11,07

Order	Cl. opp code	Opportunity	Feasibility	Impact	Total score
56 ^o	CO.WP4.34	Use of decision-making applications using AI-based systems	4,56	5,59	10,15

Table 62 - Ranking of all WP4 opportunities after the clustering.

Considering the time of execution of the VALKYRIES project, we considered the most suitable only to implement the six top-ranked clustered opportunities. This way, the chosen opportunities are the following:

- CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles.
- CO.WP4.28: Cross border data trace.
- CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges.
- CO.WP4.55: Use of wearables to support triage.
- CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms
- CO.WP4.2: Logistics assistance using UAVs.

8. Identify interdependences

This section describes which opportunities must be implemented first to achieve the target opportunity (marked in bold). That is to say, the list of opportunities on which the target opportunity depends. First, the dependencies between the top-priority opportunities of WP4 are described, and then between the top-priority opportunities of WP5 and WP6. To summarise these dependencies, Figure 4 and Figure 5 show all generated relationships.

8.1. Inside of the WP4

CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles.

CO.WP4.28: Cross border data trace: To carry out the location of the near/nearest vehicles, the information of vehicles location from different countries must be: 1) legally allowed to be shared and 2) traced to the sharing authorization.

CO.WP4.2: Logistic assistance using UAVs: To know the location of any assets, their location must be shared via the SIGRUN platform. In the case of the UAVs, the location (GNSS position) must be published as any other vehicle. In the case of the UAV position being lost (e.g., due to LoS Communication) last known position should be reported with the time of the last position available. In the case of a secondary UAV position report (air control, if applicable), special attention is to provide the data source. As a final note, the position reported is of the UAV position (3D), not of the georeferenced features from the sensors.

CO.WP4.28: Cross border data trace.

CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges: COP sharing between first response agencies within a country and/or between countries introduced through the SINGRUN architecture (D2.8) is expected to reduce voice communications.

CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles: The automatic location of emergency agency vehicles can reduce the number of voice calls in disaster management. This is because it allows emergency coordination centers to quickly identify the location and availability of resources available for dispatch to the disaster or emergency site. For example, instead of a citizen having to call the emergency coordination center to report an emergency and request assistance, the mobile application or web platform can automatically identify the location of the requester and send the information to the emergency center, which, in turn, can automatically locate the closest vehicles and dispatch them to the place of emergency. This can enable faster and more efficient responses to emergencies, reduce the workload on coordination centers and decrease the number of voice calls received.

CO.WP4.55: Use of wearable to support triage: Wearables, such as vital signs monitoring devices, can provide real-time information on the condition of the injured to emergency medical teams. This information can help prioritize care for patients based on the severity of their injuries, thereby reducing the need for multiple voice calls to coordinate care. In addition, wearables can also provide information on the location and status of first responders, which can help better coordinate search and rescue operations without the need for frequent voice calls.

CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges.

CO.WP4.15 Location of near/nearest vehicles: The automatic location of emergency agency vehicles can reduce the number of voice calls in disaster management. This is because it allows emergency coordination centres to quickly identify the location and availability of resources

available for dispatch to the disaster or emergency site. For example, instead of a citizen having to call the emergency coordination centre to report an emergency and request assistance, the mobile application or web platform can automatically identify the location of the requester and send the information to the emergency centre, which, in turn, can automatically locate the closest vehicles and dispatch them to the place of emergency. This can enable faster and more efficient responses to emergencies, reduce the workload on coordination centres and decrease the number of voice calls received.

CO.WP4.28: Cross border data trace: Cross-border data trace can reduce the number of voices calls in disaster management, as it allows response teams to have access to real-time information about the situation in different areas affected by the disaster. This can help better coordinate response operations and make faster, more informed decisions.

CO.WP4.55: Use of wearable to support triage: Wearables, such as vital signs monitoring devices, can provide real-time information on the condition of the injured to emergency medical teams. This information can help prioritize care for patients based on the severity of their injuries, thereby reducing the need for multiple voices calls to coordinate care. In addition, wearables can also provide information on the location and status of first responders, which can help better coordinate search and rescue operations without the need for frequent voice calls.

CO.WP4.55: Use of wearable to support triage.

CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles: A system where the triage will be put directly into a data system, will make it possible for the vehicles to be prioritized to the most needed casualties without any delay due to the need of transfer of information by voice between the different partners of a disaster relief operation.

CO.WP4.28: Cross border data trace: For a digital triage system to work it is very important to let the information flow between all participants regardless of country. If this is not fulfilled the whole digitalize.

CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms.

CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles: To carry out a collection of historical data from emergency situations, we must have data coming from different sources, such as locations of nearby vehicles, technological systems, or applications, among others. This is why we depend on the information collected by this opportunity to create a data dataset to use later for learning purposes or to improve procedures.

CO.WP4.55: Use of wearable to support triage: As mentioned before, historical data analysis depends on any source that provides data to the central platform (e.g., SIGRUN). The use of wearables to support triage is a data source that we will later use to store a history of emergencies, patients, etc.

CO.WP4.28: Cross border data trace: Information from cross-border data trace can be useful for historical data analysis from the missions and platforms. Based on these data and their analysis, rescue operations and coordination procedures could be improved, the response time could be reduced, and cross-border cooperation could be more efficient. Consequently, it will be beneficial to collect these data and create a dataset that decision makers can use for future rescue operations planning. Also, the dataset could be beneficial for subsequent machine learning algorithms training.

CO.WP4.2: Logistics assistances using UAVs.

CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles: A system of UAVs conducting logistic support will benefit their efficiency with the knowledge of the location of not only the nearest vehicle but all vehicles. This information, combined with an inventory list and demand list of equipment in each vehicle, will make it easy for the UAVs to know where to pick up and deliver parcels to ensure optimum equipment distribution throughout the disaster relief group.

CO.WP4.28: Cross border data trace: To use UAVs for logistics support in a cross-border disaster must have cross border data trace. Using UAVs in autonomous or semi-autonomous mode will only be possible if a regulation hampers them due to different countries.

CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms: Collection of data from all logistic assistance missions conducted will be fundamental in developing automated or autonomous logistic assistance systems where machine learning will be a vital tool.

Figure 4 - WP4 interdependencies, where each opportunity indicates the list of opportunities on which it depends.

8.2. Between the WPs

CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles.

CO.WP5.12: Standardisation of information sharing in emergency response: The sharing of the emergency response vehicle's location should follow a common method as defined in the SIGRUN architecture. Each entity sharing the vehicle information should report the last know position and its last know position time (which may be different from the time of the sharing).

CO.WP5.13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response: A common federated data model was defined, as well as a sharing protocol. Each entity sharing the common COP must ensure the proper frequency of the victims/first responders/vehicles position and status data.

CO.WP6.2: Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data: Data shared of the vehicles position data as well as victims' positioning/status should be protected against misuse and/or drop eyes also according to GDPR.

CO.WP4.28: Cross border data trace.

CO.WP6.7: Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams: As VOSTs are, in many cases, groups of virtual volunteers working and monitoring the social media content during disasters, their cooperation and coordination interface with other national and international teams by establishing technical and collaborative frameworks to enable cooperation.

CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges.

CO.WP5.12: Standardisation of information sharing in emergency response: The incident-related information transmitted in digital form follows the data structure defined in SIGRUN, which proposes standardisation data sets. The datasets are designed to share information between Agencies and between countries related to the incident. Therefore, all information that goes from being transmitted via voice to being digitised and shared on the platform must follow the rules of the SIGRUN data model and the established communication protocols.

CO.WP5.13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response: The federated data model defines a way of sharing data in terms of the data model and communication protocols.

CO.WP6.2: Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data: Shared data must be protected by the GDPR. In this respect, SIGRUN provides the basis for the model for sharing medical and security data accordingly.

CO.WP6.7: Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams: Exchange of information is done mainly in digital form, mainly when we consider the exchange of information between international teams. This reduces voice communication and leads to communication via visualisation, geolocalisation and spatial analysis using geographic information systems.

CO.WP4.55: Use of wearable to support triage.

CO.WP5.7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response: The sharing of the emergency response victim's locations/status and vehicle's location should follow a common method defined in the SIGRUN. When linked with existing triage supportive systems, the range of victims track&trace is upgraded starting from "Ground 0". Each entity sharing the victim or vehicle information should report the last know position and its last know position time (which may differ from the time of the sharing) whilst GDPR related issues are resolved due to blockchain recording of such data through the SINGRUN architecture system.

CO.WP5.13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response: A common federated data model and a sharing protocol were defined. Each entity sharing the vehicle or victim position must ensure the proper frequency of the vehicles position data, using any telecommunication system available and regardless of the lack of common technological protocols on sensors.

CO.WP6.2: Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data: Data shared of the vehicles position data should be protected against misuse using the SINGRUN architecture and recording methods of data introduced in it as a new standard.

CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms.

CO.WP5.12: Standardisation of information sharing in emergency response: This opportunity aims to store data obtained in emergency situations. These data will be based on the minimum data set established in WP5. From this set and adding new data, we will store enough information from emergencies.

CO.WP5.13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response: The main dependency we have with this opportunity is the data that is exchanged between the different systems. It depends on the data that the different sources share and send to the central platform.

CO.WP6.11: Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures with adequate field exercise program and adequate protection with risk-free activities. Historical data coming from past events for the minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers can be helpful for historical data analysis from the missions and platforms. Analysing these data, the minimum dataset could include the optimal number of competencies, and their integration into the field of operational procedures would lead to more effective and non-risky volunteers' participation in rescue operations in multi-casualty incidents.

CO.WP4.2: Logistics assistances using UAVs.

CO.WP5.7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response: Harmonized operating procedures will give one common system regarding registration of demands, update of status and so forth. One system will simplify a common logistic assistance system.

CO.WP5.12: Standardisation of information sharing in emergency response: A system running this type of logistic assistance needs one standard for information sharing. This opportunity will solve parts of this.

CO.WP6.11: Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures: Using UAVs in logistics assistance will require some basic competence for all first responders.

CO.WP6.5: Standardisation of education and training for first aid responses: It will require several levels of competence for the first responders to use a UAV in logistic assistance. It is essential to implement UAV operation in the several possible modes existing in all levels of training for first responders.

Figure 5 - Interdependences between WP4, WP5, and WP6

9. Evaluation in short of top ranked opportunities

CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles.	
Why	Sharing the location of the vehicles involved in the emergency response allows the command and medical entities to manage the response better and match the available resources to the ranking needs. The optimisation of the resources will support a lower level of victim impacts and a more efficient response of the FR and medical response that depend on knowing the position and ETA of the emergency vehicles.
How	Each vehicle control/management solution vehicle can report the GNSS position using a GNSS receiver (typically Galileo or GPS position data) and transmit its position to a central system.

Table 63 – Evaluation of the opportunity CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles.

CO.WP4.28: Cross border data trace.	
Why	Enhance the synchronization of actions/decision-making due to the same knowledge of tactical and on-field conditions on the catastrophic event, the victim's location/status, and alerts-warnings.
How	Through sharing the COP created by the SINGRUN system architecture, you linked heterogeneous federated systems (with non-compatible to each other own COPs) when exchanging the minimum data set of information according to SINGRUN specs and standards introduced.

Table 64 - Evaluation of the opportunity CO.WP4.28: Cross border data trace.

CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information	
Why	Reducing the number of voice calls in disaster management can significantly impact the effectiveness of emergency response and the ability of response teams to use their resources more efficiently. It's essential for several reasons: resources are limited. They must be used efficiently and for critical tasks, agility in emergency management (voice calls can be a slow communication) and increased accuracy and efficiency in decision-making (voice calls can be prone to errors and misunderstanding).
How	There are several ways to reduce the number of voice calls in emergency and disaster management: using mobile applications allows users to send information in real-time and receive updates in real-time, automating processes to reduce workload ante the time required to complete a task (for example, automating patient registration), using technologies for real-time collaboration and instant updating of information and using unifies communications technologies.

Table 65 - Evaluation of the opportunity CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information.

CO.WP4.55: Use of wearables to support triage	
Why	To create a new standard in triage / non triage supportive applications on victims that need / do not need hospitalization and for tracking geolocation /

CO.WP4.55: Use of wearables to support triage	
	vital signs / status data of first responders and their vehicles / supportive equipment.
How	Use NFC (or other tagging passive technologies) or a pre-established QR/Bar code marked on the bracelets, within wearables (e.g., colored bracelets) linking data related with victims' registration and follow up in Blockchain networks, as per the SINGRUN overall architecture.

Table 66 - Evaluation of the opportunity CO.WP4.55: Use of wearables to support triage.

CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms.	
Why	By storing information on past emergencies, it is possible to improve future actions and use this information to predict future trends. Analysis of these data could help us to automate decisions and thus improve response in disasters and emergency situations.
How	After storing the information of the different catastrophes that have occurred, thanks to artificial intelligence, specifically machine learning, supervised learning models can be created and used to predict events that have occurred. These models will be effective in situations where similar events are occurring to predict in advance what might happen. These predictions can also be used to learn from decisions made in emergency situations.

Table 67 - Evaluation of the opportunity CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms.

CO.WP4.2: Logistics assistance using UAVs	
Why	UAVs can provide a variety of tasks. For a disaster relief mission, searching for areas for casualties and building situational awareness will reduce the time for C2 to get a clear picture. They can be comms relay platforms making communication and coordination of the assists easier, and they can deliver parcels of necessary equipment or medicines to first responders or casualties. This work will decrease the need for people to do logistics, relieving them of first response work, and it will speed up the process of assisting casualties and getting the disaster under control.
How	By deploying UAVs in autonomous search patterns and using swarm theory. UAVs can give the almost continuous cover of the area to give situation awareness and communications opportunities for the first responders and C2. A common data platform like SINGRUN will provide everyone involved with the same information and the possibility to get essential equipment by UAV delivery systems. Machine learning will improve the system's ability to deliver the optimum service.

Table 68 - Evaluation of the opportunity CO.WP4.2: Logistics assistance using UAVs.

10. Roadmap for pre-standardisation

Until now, we studied the most prioritised opportunities in depth in this deliverable. However, all these opportunities need to be pre-standardised. This way, establishing a set of steps and goals is necessary to achieve the pre-standardisation. In other words, a roadmap is a guide which establishes the criteria and processes that must be followed to evaluate the feasibility and impact of the opportunities before they are adopted as a standard in Europe.

10.1. WP roadmap

In this section, we will describe at a general level the most common steps to achieve the pre-standardisation of the opportunities. Subsequently, we will go through the steps that have to be taken for individual opportunities. Figure 6 shows the more common steps or goals and the corresponding dates to achieve the pre-standardisation. The steps are the following:

- Demo VALKYRIES: The opportunity will be demonstrated during the use cases.
- Several scientific publications: The results obtained will be documented through several publications.
- Evaluation of technologies: Once the opportunity is demonstrated, it is necessary to study if the technologies used during the use cases are the most suitable. Otherwise, we would need to study other options in depth to improve the results that VALKYRIES aims to achieve.
- Define consensus in a country: Before achieving a pre-standardisation at the Europe level, it is necessary to define a consensus in a simple country, for example, the country where the opportunity was demonstrated in Valkyries.
- Define consensus in EU: If experts from a unique country validate the opportunity, it could be a first step towards the pre-standardisation at the European Union level.
- Request standardisation: Finally, the last step consists in requesting standardisation which the European Commission will validate.

Figure 6 - General roadmap steps.

10.2. Opportunity roadmap

In this section, we will go deeper into the steps that we consider necessary to achieve the pre-standardisation of each of the six top-ranked WP4 opportunities.

10.2.1. CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles

To carry out a pre-standardisation of this opportunity, the steps identified in Figure 7 and explained below must be performed:

Figure 7 - Roadmap for CO.WP4.15 Location of near/nearest Vehicle.

1. DEMO VALKYRIES (June 2023 – September 2023).

In UC1 (and potentially in the other UC where location capability is available), the vehicles' position is shared, allowing to optimise the management of the situation and the allocation of a vehicle to a victim. Several solutions can be used to report the position of the vehicle, but it is critical to validate how this information is timely disseminated through the SIGRUN and to the VALKYRIES application that requires such data.

2. SEVERAL SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS (October 2023 – April 2024).

The next steps will be to gather the operational results by having the vehicle's location and crossing with the victim's location (self-reported or via a directly a third-party artifact, e.g. first responder cell phone). Analyse the performance of operation and disseminate through the scientific community the wins and pitfall of the used approach. The exploitation of the results will focus on the operational benefits (not on the technological aspects), such as: the timing of the medical response by establishing ETA of an ambulance arrival to hospital effect; Tracing victim's position towards the medical response, especially on low priority victims (where several victims are lost during an MCI).

3. EVALUATION OF THE MOST SUITABLE TECHNOLOGIES AND TOOLS FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION (May 2024 – December 2024).

In parallel to the previous step, the three key technologies required to perform the operation will be evaluated towards the definition of the minimum requirements:

1. Miniaturized GNSS receivers (Galileo/GPS) portable and easily plugged in to the vehicles, with connection to an IP network.
2. Communication network channels (4G/5G, WIFI, other) that can support the plug-in of the miniaturized GNSS (point 1).
3. Data models modelling to register, process and record the data shared by the vehicle GNSS.

4. DEFINE CONSENSUS IN A COUNTRY (January 2025 - July 2025).

Once we have the acceptance of the scientific community, the solutions must be further operated by first responders' organizations in a country and involve high impact organisations at national level and invite organisation from different EU countries. The goal is to generate consensus among these organization and gather interest to conduct operational experiments in other countries.

5. DEFINE CONSENSUS IN EU (August 2025 - April 2026).

Continuing the previous step, the purpose of this phase is to build EU-level consensus on the supporting function, not so much on the technologies. Because this will impact sensitive assets, such as firefighting vehicles and victim's ambulances, entities with regulatory and certification competencies shall be involved. Further steps towards the discussion and agreements at the EU level regarding harmonising the functions required for the emergency response systems will be taken. Performing joint demonstrations and discussions regarding cross-border events will be conducted. The aim is to agree on a minimum common position and rationale that can be used to pave the way towards a complete harmonization under the European Union leadership.

6. REQUEST STANDARDISATION (May 2026 – Nov 2026, and ongoing).

With enough organisations agreeing and having consensus from several countries, the standardisation process will start. Parallel to this work, to increase the number of organisations and countries will continue, combined with current manufacturers of the industry of these assets and gather the EU Emergency Response enterprises ecosystem to become early adopters of the solution and integrate it into their commercial offers.

10.2.2. CO.WP4.28: Cross border data trace

1. DEMO VALKYRIES (May 2023 – September 2023).

- a. In all UCs trials and evaluations against existing manual or other systems, different configurations of federated systems and external data mapping in COPs will be used in order to measure the impact. Such COPs will be exchanged between cross-border agencies in all UCs, in order to ensure the technological, workflow and organizational impacts from the use of the SINGRUN as a standardisation vehicle around EU
- b. Replication of common regulatory between other cross border countries (May 5th – Until September 23rd)

In all UCs, the already defined internal procedures of the SINGRUN operational centre in WP5 (internal Deliverable ID5.3) and the availability of a minimum set of data visible by all engaged agencies (Name of the Rescue Plan, Responsible for cross border communications, names, and communication data of technical administrators etc) are expected to reduce traced difficulties

through the introduction of a minimum standard following also the Guidelines of other EU related projects.

- c. Warnings and alarms in cross-border data trace and exchange (June 23 until September 23)

In UCs 2,3 and 4, the mapping of alarms and warnings by different agents within each country will be mapped in COPs exchanged. So, there is a new opportunity to monitor public reactions (through social media or other cross-border sources) to evaluate the impact of such alarming or to trace any false information (only in UC2, through virtual teams).

2. CONSENSUS WITHIN A COUNTRY (June 23rd to December 30th 2023).

A first consensus from at least one EU country is expected in Bulgaria, having committed already to introduce the results and recommendations to local authorities. Most expected date to create a first consensus is September 1st 2023.

3. PROPOSE NEW STANDARD IN EU (June-July 2023 until the end of 2023).

Following the execution and tests/valuations of UC1, 2 and 3, there will be enough evidence to present well recorded data and measurable impacts to EU as a first step for pre-standardisation of the SINGRUN architecture and its internal procedures.

10.2.3. CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges

To carry out a pre-standardisation of this opportunity, the steps identified in Figure 8 and explained below must be performed:

Figure 8 - Roadmap for CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges.

1. DEMO VALKYRIES (May 2023 – October 2023).

The SINGRUN platform and mobile applications will be used for all UC to share information between the mobile devices and the Command and Control station. The data set will be

according to the data model defined in Valkyries and agreed upon by the consortium and according to the interoperability model established by SIGRUN. In all UCs, KPIs will be established to measure improvements in management times using mobile triage applications and Command and Control applications according to SIGRUN. In addition, operational improvements in user experience and usability of the tools will be evaluated from the point of view of improving the decision-making process.

2. SEVERAL SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS (November 2023 – March 2024).

Several articles will be published in scientific journals showing the interoperability model offered by Valkyries and, in particular, the digitalisation of the triage process and integration and visualisation of related medical information in Command and Control applications from the point of view of improving communication via voice and reducing manual work in incident management. In the articles, the value will be given to the KPIs of improvement and optimisation of the management times of a multi-victim incident contrasted with the accurate data of the different UC and compared with traditional systems.

3. EVALUATION OF THE MOST SUITABLE TECHNOLOGIES AND TOOLS FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION (April 2024 – December 2024).

The reduction of calls and work automation can be improved by applying various current technologies. At the triage level and in terms of communications, triage data is sent via radio, and no applications are available to digitalise this data. The use of an application that, on the one hand, digitises the data and sends it via alternative communications (4G, 5G, local WIFI) could be critical in these cases. Ensuring the availability of communications in these situations is key to using digitisation systems.

On the other hand, having platforms that ensure the interoperability of emergency management applications focused on the digitalization of triage data facilitates incident management. VALKYRIES defines a Minimum Data Set and an interoperability model for data communication to the different Command and Control applications.

Additionally, to improve automation, the Command and Control tools themselves have automation tools (process workflows) and increasingly allow the integration of other sensors (cameras, wearables) and other external systems (satellite data), facilitating decision-making and reducing manual work. The SIGRUN platform contemplates these processes and defines an interoperability model to include these elements.

4. DEFINE CONSENSUS IN A COUNTRY (January 2025 – June 2025).

Once we have the scientific consensus, we will look for the adoption of the interoperability model between Agencies in the same country, as there is also a problem of interoperability between the different Agencies. In this sense, the use of the SIGRUN platform will facilitate the sharing of data between the different national agencies in an agile manner. This standardisation will involve, on the one hand, the adaptation of current Command and Control applications and the design of new native applications with the model defined in SIGRUN. Based on the authorities that have participated in the UC and the FR involved, we will promote national presentations of the results of Valkyries with FR entities and 112-type incident management entities to disseminate the interoperability model offered by Valkyries so that it can be a design basis for current and future applications in the field of emergency management.

5. DEFINE CONSENSUS IN EU (July 2025 – June 2026).

Once we have the scientific consensus, we will look to adopt the interoperability model between Agencies in the same country, as there is also an interoperability problem between the different Agencies. In this sense, using the SIGRUN platform will facilitate the sharing of data between the different national agencies in an agile manner. This standardisation will involve, on the one hand, the adaptation of current Command and Control applications and the design of new native applications with the model defined in SIGRUN. Based on the authorities that have participated in the UC and the FR involved, we will promote national presentations of the results of Valkyries with FR entities and 112-type incident management entities to disseminate the interoperability model offered by Valkyries so that it can be a design basis for current and future applications in the field of emergency management.

6. REQUEST STANDARDISATION (July 2026 – June 2027 and on going).

Finally, with the national and European consensus, the scientific publications and the demonstrations that have been carried out in the different UCs with the proposed technology, the last step is to promote standardisation centred on the interoperability model defined by Valkyries.

10.2.4. CO.WP4.55: Use of wearable to support triage

1. DEMO VALKYRIES (From June 21 – Until September 23rd).

In UC3, UC4 and UC2 as an alternative to triage system, in UC1 as a registration and track& trace of victims that need no hospitalization. Following the proof of concept using wearables in both cases, a pre-standardisation effort will be supported at least one scientific article to appear as well as to primary acceptance by at least one Civil Protection Authority as a National pre-standards (Bulgaria and/or Greece)

2. SEVERAL SCIENTIFIC PUBS (From March 30 – Until September 30th).

The next step to be taken once the datasets are unified and fully functional is their acceptance by the scientific community. This acceptance will give us the confirmation that these datasets are correct and solve the proposed problem. This process consists of the creation of different scientific articles and their subsequent publication as well as the attendance to different scientific conferences. Once these articles are accepted and published, we can safely say that we have a product that can be standardized.

3. Evaluation of the most suitable technologies and tools for the implementation (From June 23rd – Until September 30th).

What technologies, data, etc., are most suitable will be evaluated during UCs. Then final configurations will be adjusted for further standardisation steps.

4. DEFINE CONSENSUS IN A COUNTRY (From June 23rd – Until December 30th 2023).

Once we have the acceptance of the scientific community, we have to get our product (datasets) to be used by some organizations, in this case the organization that we want to use our products would be our country. When we achieve that our datasets are used in such an important

organization as a country and we achieve that harmonization by all the companies of the country, we are achieving the first part of our purpose, which is the establishment of our datasets as a "standard", that is to say that the whole country unifies its datasets and the information that is stored is the same for all.

5. DEFINE CONSENSUS IN EU (From January 1st– Until September 30th) 2024.

When we have this harmonization or this use of the datasets/communication/terminals by one country, we will try to get the other countries of our community, specifically Europe, to use these datasets to store emergency information. This step will give us a lot of strength with a view to standardisation, since being accepted by the scientific community and being used by such an important organization as the European Union will lead to harmonization in a large part of the world territory.

6. REQUEST STANDARDISATION (From September 1st– Until September 30th).

Finally, once the standard are being used by so many organizations and have been validated by them, we will proceed to contact the standardizing unit and we will proceed to write the request to standardize our datasets worldwide. In this request we will have to give strong reasons that demonstrate the functionality of these datasets, as well as show that they are already being used by many companies, organizations, etc.

10.2.5. CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms

To carry out a pre-standardisation of this opportunity, the steps identified in Figure 9 and explained below must be performed:

Figure 9 - Roadmap for CO.WP4.21 Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms.

1. DEMO VALKYRIES (May 2023 – June 2023).

The first step to carrying out the process of standardizing something is to have it and make it functional, that is why we must have implemented the datasets used in the VALKYRIES demos. After this implementation, we have the acquisition of the data from the demos and, finally, to complete this step, verification concerning the creating, correction and unification of the

datasets created. This step is very important because it is the initial step, and we need it to be able to start this whole process.

2. ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS OBTAINED DURING THE DEMO (July 2023 – September 2023)

Once the opportunity has been evaluated during the use case according to several metrics, the next step consists of analysing in depth some considerations. Firstly, we will check if the features (minimum dataset + additional metadata) are the most suitable for the scenario we want to solve. Consequently, we should update some of them, add new ones or remove existing ones. Secondly, this process allows us to evaluate if the amount of gathered data and the models generated subsequently using it are good enough for the scope Valkyries wants to solve. Finally, another step for evaluation will be applied.

3. SEVERAL COMPARISONS BETWEEN THE DATASETS DEVELOPED AND THOSE IN THE LITERATURE (October 2023 – December 2023).

The comparison between the developed dataset and those available in the literature is a vital step to know if our dataset is a good solution in such emergency scenarios. Additionally, this comparison will be helpful to comment on the scientific publications in the next step of the roadmap of this opportunity.

4. SEVERAL SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS (January 2024 – October 2024).

Once the datasets are unified and fully functional, the next step to be taken is their acceptance by the scientific community. This acceptance will confirm that these datasets are correct and solve the proposed problem. This process consists in creating scientific journal articles and conference publications to disseminate the results of the work performed in VALKYRIES. Once these articles are accepted and published, they can serve as a first step toward the standardisation of this opportunity.

5. DEFINE CONSENSUS IN A COUNTRY (November 2024 – August 2025).

Once we have the acceptance of the scientific community, it is essential to have consensus within a country, in terms of the procedures and goals to achieve for this opportunity. When we achieve that the datasets are used in such an important organization as a country and we achieve that harmonization by all the agencies of the country, we are achieving the first part of our purpose, which is the establishment of our datasets as a "national standard", that is to say that the whole country unifies its datasets and the information that is stored is the same for all.

6. DEFINE CONSENSUS IN EU (September 2025 – April 2026).

When we have this harmonization or this use of the datasets by one country, we will try to get the other countries of our community, specifically Europe, to use these datasets to store emergency information. This step will give us much strength with a view to standardisation since being accepted by the scientific community and being used by such an important organization as the European Union will lead to harmonization in large parts of the world territory.

7. REQUEST STANDARDISATION (After May 2026).

Finally, once the datasets are being used by so many organizations and have been validated by them, we will proceed to contact the adequate standardising unit, and we will proceed to write the request to standardize our datasets worldwide. In this request, we will have to give strong

reasons that demonstrate the functionality of these datasets and show that many companies, organizations, etc., are already using them.

10.2.6. CO.WP4.2: Logistics assistances using UAVs

To carry out a pre-standardisation of this opportunity, the steps identified in Figure 10 and explained below must be performed:

Figure 10 - Roadmap for CO.WP4.21 Logistics assistance using UAVs

1. DEMO VALKYRIES (June 2023 – October 2023).

In UC4 and UC2 to demonstrate different tasks UAVs can conduct regarding search & relief, parcel delivery and information gathering.

2. SEVERAL SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS (November 2023 – January 2024).

Some demonstrations will be part of other research projects working with UAVs. These projects will produce several scientific papers that will give a deeper understanding of how UAVs will assist in both the practical and technical aspects of logistics. This will teach us what standardisation of technology, procedures and training should look like.

3. EVALUATION OF THE MOST SUITABLE TECHNOLOGIES AND TOOLS FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION (February 2024 – October 2024).

There are several different areas a UAV can assist in rescue missions where very specific technologies must be used, example is tools to detect radioactive substances. But some main topics will be prioritized. Firstly, regardless of what assistance the UAV is intended to give, Live HD feedback is essential. To really have benefit from the drone, the data collected must be presented in real time to the appropriate personnel for them to take necessary actions. So high quality and stable communication is vital, this will as a side effect enable the UAV to act as a communication relay station, to further secure the live communication in the whole operation.

The communication system must be standardized throughout the EU to secure seamless operations regardless of borders. Other tools that must be evaluated and tested is:

- Camera technology for detecting (thermal cameras), identification (Zoom camera) and wide area surveillance (wide angel cameras).
- Two-way communication to let the first responders interact with casualties or lost people through the UAV.
- Systems to deliver payloads like tools, first aid kits or medicines.
- Good navigation system to work autonomous, give correct positions of findings and let operator remotely operate drones in difficult or congested areas.

4. DEFINE CONSENSUS IN A COUNTRY (November 2024- December 2025).

Once we accept the scientific community, the system must be tested by first responders' organisations in a country. These tests must expand into high-impact organisations and organisations present in several different EU countries. The milestone is to have consensus from several high-impact organisations in several countries; then, further work can be conducted within several countries to get consensus in most of them.

5. DEFINE CONSENSUS IN EU (January 2026 - December 2026).

When we have this harmonization or this use of the datasets/communication/terminals by one country, we will try to get the other countries of our community, specifically Europe, to use these datasets to store emergency information. This step will give us much strength with a view to standardisation since being accepted by the scientific community and being used by such an important organization as the European Union will lead to harmonization in large parts of the world territory.

6. REQUEST STANDARDISATION (January 2027 an ongoing).

With enough organisations agreeing and having consensus from several countries, the standardisation process will start. Parallel to this work, to increase the number of organisations and countries will continue.

11. Stakeholders' evaluation

As part of validation of the clustering, analysis and, prioritisation process done in this WP4, we shared a questionnaire with the VALKYRIES External Advisory Boards and stakeholders where they must evaluate the process followed and the six WP4 top-ranked opportunities from the following questions:

1. General question: What is your level of acceptance of the harmonization strategy?
2. For each opportunity: Do you consider that this aggregated opportunity presents a high impact and feasibility to be implanted in the EU?

The questionnaire was answered by four persons, and their answers are shown in the following table.

What is your level of acceptance of the harmonization strategy?		
Person I	Agree.	
Person II	I firmly believe that the harmonization strategy is well oriented and will deliver results	
Person III	High	
Person IV	High	
Person V	Harmonization process is always difficult one but any effort to achieve common strategy has to be considered as success. So, I accept positively the results of VALKYRIES project in this direction.	
Do you consider that this aggregated opportunity presents a high impact and feasibility to be implanted in the EU?		
Person I	CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles	Yes
	CO.WP4.28: Cross border data trace	Not actually
	CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges	Yes
	CO.WP4.55: Use of wearable to support triage	Yes
	CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms	Slightly agree
	CO.WP4.2: Logistics assistances using UAVs	Agree
Person II	CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles	I have no doubt about the impact, which will be high and very favourable, the location of the closest mobile resources is essential to address there very complicated situations, however, the extension and acceptance to be implemented by all the participants is something that will also depend on many other variables, especially economics, since the different parties involved usually have their own tools that rarely work with open standard
	CO.WP4.28: Cross border data trace	This case is even more important than that of the vehicles, the traceability of those

		affected in cross-border incidents acquires vital importance, both for the human and social component and for the economic component. Here I do believe that the implication to standardise the measures under development will be much more intense.
	CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges	It is the current trend to digitise as much data as possible in order to extract all the relevant information that helps in event management and reduce the “noise” caused by excessive superfluous communications. It is the fundamental pillar on which everything must resolve: collecting, and sharing, and for this it is essential to have most of the information digitised.
	CO.WP4.55: Use of wearable to support triage	The issue of wearables, while promising, needs to be approached with particular caution in order to ensure the right balance between privacy and external exposure. It is understandable that a large part of the society are leaders in the sharing of their data, but there are ethical and legal aspects that should be taken into account, and, above all, they should be very well explained to citizens.
	CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms	It is essential that records of the activity carried out are kept in order to be able to compare future events and to be able to draw conclusions and adopt the most and best studied measures. Not only this, but they can also serve as a basis for future extrapolations and as a starting point for new comparable developments.
	CO.WP4.2: Logistics assistances using UAVs	-
Person III	CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles	Agree.
	CO.WP4.28: Cross border data trace	Agree.
	CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges	Agree.
	CO.WP4.55: Use of wearable to support triage	Fully agree.
	CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms	Fully agree.
	CO.WP4.2: Logistics assistances using UAVs	Needs more study.

Person IV	CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles	Yes.
	CO.WP4.28: Cross border data trace	Yes.
	CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges	No.
	CO.WP4.55: Use of wearable to support triage	No.
	CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms	Yes.
	CO.WP4.2: Logistics assistances using UAVs	Yes.
Person V	CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles	Important feature in respect of first response time. This information should be activated in case of emergency and not to be supported all the time and should be well protected.
	CO.WP4.28: Cross border data trace	Most complicated problem in both legal and technical terms. In some cases even at national level the data exchange between national systems is an issue. Some agreed SOP could be the right approach.
	CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges	For both voice and digital communication, the most important is availability. In some cases, voice is more operational.
	CO.WP4.55: Use of wearable to support triage	Easy and quick pattern to support triage.
	CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms	Historical data analysis could be more efficient at national level as data formats, languages, and knowledge differs from country to country. This could be useful for the future when harmonized data can be used for AI solutions.
	CO.WP4.2: Logistics assistances using UAVs	Yes. Wide area of use and improvement of technical aspects.

Table 69 - Answers given by EABs consultation in the questionnaire.

12. Conclusions

This deliverable describes the impact and feasibility of each opportunity proposed in deliverables D4.2 (first version) and D4.6 through their impact and feasibility scores. Subsequently, a ranking has been made based on the sum of each opportunity's impact and feasibility ratings to select the six opportunities with the highest rating and thus be able to analyse the dependencies of the opportunities in this WP and between WP5 and WP6. Finally, a roadmap was drawn for each of the six selected opportunities.

12.1. Conclusions CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles

In the current state of the technology, it makes poor sense that geo data of the critical key assets involved in an MCI response must be discovered. The benefits are enormous as it enables better management of the assets in the field of operations, conducting a faster and more adequate medical response, from the front-end first responders to the Hospital providing the medical support. In a context where some MCI events, such as wild forest fires or floods, tend to become more frequent, the impact on lives and society is more disruptive. Therefore, it is most important to effectively manage the assets and minimize the impact of such MCI events.

Geo-managing an event implies that the position of the actors in an event is known; for that, it requires positioning solutions, connectivity and communication solutions and data management solutions combined. However, many different systems, applications and legacy solutions come into a common operation with typical integration difficulties. So, this opportunity plays a high role in the integration as it aims to harmonise a small but critical system function, which is the sharing of the location actors and asset's location through a joint federated Force.

12.2. Conclusions CO.WP4.28: Cross border data trace

Blockchain logging of all exchanged data between federated systems within a country or in cross-border incidents allow the execution of queries on historical data exchanged between countries (following the bilateral permissions). As those data include the defined minimum data sets and meta file information, transparency and security in such traces is achieved.

For the UCs, a predefined set of queries need to be defined.

12.3. Conclusions CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges

Reducing telephone communication and automating emergency-related processes can be feasible with today's technologies.

The telephone communication can easily be replaced by tools that allow digitisation and data transmission. To implement these tools, reliable communication networks must be guaranteed in emergencies other than the current radio-based ones (4G, 5G or local WIFI).

On the other hand, current Command and Control applications must improve their interoperability so that third-party applications can be easily integrated (triage applications, integration of third-party geolocation systems, integration of external satellite systems). And they must be prepared to face the integration of new sensors with IoT technologies (Body Cams, wearables, drones, and sensors with terrain information).

The Command and Control tools may include tools for process improvement (task automation, logistics system integration), but many involve integrating third-party systems.

Interoperability must be ensured between cross border emergencies, but first, this level of interoperability must be ensured between the agencies themselves at the national level that does not share information (triage data, vehicle location, tactical information, drone information). Many of the Command and Control applications used in emergency management centres are improving inter-agency and generic interoperability from the platform to integrate thirty-part systems easily.

The results of the project focused on the SINGRUN platform responding to these needs and defining a data model for sending triage data and defining an interoperability model that allows existing applications to be connected and also defines a model that serves to design new applications, acting as a platform that guarantees interoperability between the different applications for managing an emergency incident.

12.4. Conclusions CO.WP4.55: Use of wearable to support triage

Using wearables as part of the triage procedure can expand the tractability of victims from “Ground zero” to the secured area when the victim is handled by first rescuers to EMS.

The same methodology can be used to track and trace method for victims not needing hospitalization (internal “refugees”) that need to be treated by different first respond agencies or municipality services.

The opportunity also, as part of the SINGRUN architecture defined in D2.8 (9), create a sound background for interoperability as far as no common communication protocols or standards exist in the wearable sensors industry.

In conclusion, this opportunity expands the effectiveness of existing federated systems and services of first responders to victims.

12.5. Conclusions CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms

In today's world, emergencies and disasters have become more frequent and unpredictable, and they can happen anywhere and anytime. The impact of these incidents can be devastating, leading to loss of life, property damage, and economic disruption. In response to this reality, it has become increasingly important for organizations to have effective emergency management plans in place that can minimize the impact of such incidents.

This opportunity is focused on one of the critical components of any emergency management plan which is the ability to analyse past incidents and responses. By examining past incidents and responses, organizations can identify areas for improvement, such as better resource allocation or more effective communication. This knowledge can help organizations optimize their response efforts by allocating resources more effectively, making better decisions in the heat of the moment, and improving communication among team members and with external partners.

In addition to improving the efficiency and effectiveness of emergency response efforts, the analysis of past incidents and responses can also help organizations prepare for future incidents. By identifying patterns and trends, organizations can develop proactive plans and strategies that are tailored to the specific risks they face. For example, if an organization is in an area that is prone to flooding, they can use past incident data to identify the most vulnerable areas and develop plans to mitigate the impact of future floods.

In conclusion, the opportunity is very important in emergency scenarios. Their impact and feasibility scores, and the deadlines considered in the roadmap corroborate that it is a suitable opportunity to be implemented in the VALKYRIES project.

12.6. Conclusions CO.WP4.2: Logistics assistances using UAVs

The technological development of unmanned vehicles has made great progress in the last decade and is still progressing at a great speed. All types of UVs will be of assistance for disaster relief, but UAVs have shown the most potential. Using UAVs will reduce the workload on first responders since they can conduct search and relief missions, deliver parcels and equipment and work as comms relay platforms. Artificial intelligence and machine learning development mean they will work autonomously, assisting the first responders as needed. The procedures, standards, rules and so forth must be standardized throughout the EU so cross-border and cross-departmental use can happen without too much delay and bureaucracy.

13. Annex A – References and bibliography

1. **Consortium, VALKYRIES.** *Deliverable D4.6, "Harmonization opportunities on the technological landscape for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters"*. 2023.
2. **Consortium, VALKYRIES.** *Deliverable D5.3, "Roadmap for enhancing the pan-European operational and procedural capabilities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters"*. 2023.
3. **Consortium, VALKYRIES.** *Deliverable D6.3: "Roadmap for enhancing the Pan-European preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters"*. 2023.
4. **Consortium, VALKYRIES.** *Deliverable D4.2, "Harmonization opportunities on the technological landscape for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters"*. 2022.
5. **Consortium, VALKYRIES.** *Deliverable D2.2, "Terminology and semantics"*. 2022.
6. **International Organization for Standardization.** *ISO/IEC 11581-40:2011*. 2017.
7. **European Commission.** *Art. 6 GDPR: Lawfulness of processing*. 2016.
8. —. *Art. 9 GDPR: Processing of special categories of personal data*. 2016.
9. **Consortium, VALKYRIES.** *Deliverable 2.8: "Architecture Design Document M12"*. 2022.

14. Annex B – Glossary

Acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ETA	Estimated Time of Arrival
FR	First Responder
GPS	Global Positioning System
SDN	Software Defined Network
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
EU	European Union
EC	European Commission
MCI	Mass Casualty Incident
SIoT	Satellite Internet of Things

Table 70 - Glossary